

LIFEFORCE

Lesson structure

To Begin:

Introduction: LIFEFORCE song, Mascots, Posters
(Only for the first lesson)

LIFEFORCE principles [5'-10']

Warm-up activities* Choose one of the following: [5'-10']

- Introductory Breathing Games [Activity 1]
- Warm up (Physical, Personal, Team & Yoga) [Activity 2]
- Unblocking & cognitive games [Activity 3]
- Confidence games [Activity 4]

Main session (Choose one or some of the following):

- Body Anatomy*
- Vocabulary
- Social-Emotional skills**
- Breathing games*
- LIFEFORCE BLS Algorithm
- Foreign Body Airway Obstruction
- LIFEFORCE BLS scenarios
- LIFEFORCE Music (Songs, music activities - games)**
- LIFEFORCE BLS Yoga poses & games*
- Language-Communication skills
- Cognitive-Perceptual skills

To End:

Closing activities* Choose one of the following:

- Memory and Concentration games [5'-10']
- Relaxation [3'-5']
- Reflection & Team Goal [5'-10']

* Body awareness is a section that is most crucial to the program, as LIFEFORCE BLS-Algorithm is totally connected with the body and the sense of the body, which is why it covers almost every aspect of the program.

Body Awareness consists of the following thematic sections: Warm-up Activities, Body Anatomy, Breathing Games, LIFEFORCE Yoga Poses and Closing Activities.

** These two thematic sections can be used in any or even all three parts of the lesson structure (Begin, Main, End).

Bloom's Taxonomy

Suggested Questions-LOTS

Level 1: Remember

1. Describe what happened when...?
2. Can you list three...?
3. Do you remember...?
4. How would you describe...?
5. How many...?
6. What happened after/before...?
7. Why/When/Who/Which/Where...?

Level 2: Understand

1. What is/was the main idea of...? (8-10 years old)
2. Can you distinguish between...?
3. What were the differences between...?
4. Can you explain what is happening / what is meant . . . ?
5. Can you give a reason for..?
6. How is... feeling?
7. What do you think will happen next...?

Level 3: Apply

1. Could this have happened in...?
2. How could you use this ...?
3. How would you solve _____ using what you have learned...?
4. How would you show your understanding of...?
5. What would you have done in the same situation?
6. What would happen if...?
7. What examples can you find to...?

Suggested Questions-HOTS

Level 4: Analyze

1. Can you identify the main idea /character / events...?
2. Can you list the parts...?
3. How is _____ related to...?
4. What motive is there...?
5. What are/were the (dis)advantages of x?
6. What were the causes of x?
7. What conclusions can you draw...?

Level 5: Evaluate

1. Determine the most important points of the scenario and rank them in order...?
2. Can you propose an alternative...?
3. Suppose you could _____ what would you do...?
4. Do you think x was a good thing?
5. Do you agree/disagree that...?
6. What made this (un)successful? Why?
7. How would you improve...?

Level 6: Create

1. Can you compose a song about...?
2. Can you think of another suitable title for x?
3. Can you see another solution to...?
4. How many ways can you...?
5. What information was used to make the conclusion...?
6. How do you think x would feel?
7. What would you do differently next time?

Bloom's Taxonomy - Suggested Activities-LOTS

Level 1

- Arrange scrambled story scenes in sequence
- Identify most important attributes of main
- Create a chart / picture / diagram of the information

Level 2

- Write a summary of the main events (8-10 years old)
- Retell the story in your own words
- Predict what could happen next in the story

Level 3

- Make a scenario to show how it works
- Rewrite/describe the scene according to how you would react
- Transfer the main character/situation to a different setting
- Produce examples from real life based on the central problem in the story

Suggested Activities-HOTS

Level 4

- Select the parts of the story that were the most exciting, happiest, saddest, believable, fantastic etc.
- Distinguish between events in the story that are critical and less important
- Compare and contrast two important characters/situations

Level 5

- Assess the value of the story
- Compare and contrast this story with another you have experienced
- Judge the main characters and their actions
- Judge the main characters and their actions from a moral or ethical point of view

Level 6

- Compose an internal monologue for the main character during a pivotal moment
- Imagine you are one of the characters and write a diary entry
- Create a new character and explain how they would fit into the story
- Changing the setting and the characters, retell the story in your own words

Engagement

Silhouettes

Students create altogether an outline of an image that represents a topic or subject & fill the center of it with relevant drawings, images & words. It is used to showcase key facts about story characters, historical figures, countries & other areas of study.

Listening Dyads

A communication strategy in which a question is posed & each student in a paired relationship answers in turns. Listeners are expected to be fully attentive but cannot interrupt the speaker for any reason. At the end of the speaker's time, the students change roles.

First-After Board

A visual display of 2 sequential tasks, using picture icons. The activity displayed under/next to the "first" section is the one that the student is currently working on & the activity displayed under the "then" section is the one that will follow after the student finishes with the first task.

Cooperative learning

Students can approach learning opportunities in peer groups, usually in teams of 4 where each member has a specific role (time-keeper, note-maker, discussion leader & reporter).

Mindfulness Break

The students are guided through consciously calming their minds & bodies in order to focus their attention on the present moment. They remain quietly seated for 60", using their senses to take in observations.

Representation

Everyday Sign Language

Can be taught and used by all students to express their feelings throughout the school day. Combines simultaneously hand shapes, orientation, movement and facial expression.

Word Wall

A bulletin board or chart listing high-frequency or content-specific words in alphabetical order. Instead of being a static display of words, Word Walls intend to grow throughout a unit or year as the teacher adds new words providing students with repetitive exposure to key-terms.

Songs, Raps and Chants

Repeated practice with a selected or created song, rap or chant provides students with the opportunity to learn from pattern and rhythm conversational language, vocabulary, even mathematical facts.

Somebody Wanted But So Then

A summarizing strategy that uses a series of prompts to name key-fictional story elements. Each word in the name of the strategy is used to help students focus on different aspects of a text (e.g. Somebody: Who is the main character? |Wanted: What are they trying to achieve? |But: What issue do they face? |So: How do they attempt to fix it? |Then: What happened in the end?)

UDL - Expression

Preferred Modes of Expression

Students are given the choice of different methods to express themselves (e.g. verbal responses, drawing, acting /movement demonstration) when presenting information or understanding of what they have learned.

Write Around

Students take turns responding to an open-ended question, in a small group setting with each member elaborating on the previous responses. The first student in each group is given 30" to write a response. Then, the paper gets passed to the next group member who has an additional 30" to read the response after adding, clarifying or expanding any information as they respond. When all students have contributed, groups have a several minute discussion before participating in a whole-class share.

Picture Story Telling

Instead of producing a written paragraph or essay describing material that has been read, the student produces a visual story that captures the same elements that a written piece requires (e.g. details, sequencing of events, evidence, etc.)

Sentence Starters

Provide a frame for students to express their thoughts in writing or speaking. Common uses are to help students in describing facts, making predictions, comparing and contrasting, starting an opinion and clarifying or paraphrasing information.

Total Physical Response

Students listen to commands and respond with physical actions and movements (e.g. as simple as moving a finger in a specific way to more complex actions involving the whole body) in order to connect a physical association to a concept that is being taught (e.g. new vocabulary, complex processes, etc.)

Give One-Get One

Students intentionally seek and share information with one another. First, they write down several ideas to a prompt provided by the teacher. Then, they circulate the classroom and pair up with partners. Each time, they “give” (share) one idea and “get” one. At the end, the class discusses the key ideas they learned from one another.

I-messages

A statement about one’s feelings or beliefs expressed as a 3-part model sentence: 1. I feel... (feeling) 2. when... (what caused the feeling) 3. I would like... (what you want to happen instead). For example, a student might say: “I feel anxious because I won’t be able to finish on time. I would like if you could give me back my pencil” instead of “You are hogging my pencil.”

BEGIN

- Among the Beginning activities, choose the one(s) that you think the children need more at the current time!
- Music games & activities can be carried out on any of the 3 sessions of the lesson (begin, main, end) as well as social-emotional awareness activities.
- During any discussion or lesson introduction, remember to activate children's prior knowledge (with fun ways) and give them time and space to express themselves.
- Use the UDL engagement tips and videos (in teacher's handbook) to engage as more children as you can and have a successful lesson!
- Don't forget to remind the children of what activities will come next, in other words to give them an idea of the lesson structure, so that they feel more as a part of it.
- Remember to represent the learning information to the children in more than one ways. This is also a way to boost their learning through repetition!
- Make sure you have used the UDL proposals to enhance children's ways of expression (in Teacher's handbook). You can watch the suggested videos as well!
- The two-line rime/target used in the beginning and the end of the lessons will function in a fun and unifying way reminding the children of their goal!
- Use the activities in both your and the children's interests and have some fun. They are designed to be this way!

Begin - Introductory Breath (1)

Hero(in)e's Suit

- Imagine a zipper beginning from under the belly button reaching up to the nose.
 - Breathe in, zip up to the nose and hold breath. Put the other hand on the belly to feel how it is expanding while breathing.
 - Breathe out, zip down to the belly button and exhale, feeling now the belly going in.
- Repeat 3-5 times.

Notes: Children imagine they put on the superhero(in)e suit, ready for action. Now they need to zip it up. While breathing in, children are getting full of oxygen, in other words power, which they need. While breathing out, they are spreading their power as far as they can, rising to their toes like superhero(in)es taking off.

*Instead of "breathe in" use "have a smell" for 6-8 years old.

Introductory Breath (2)

Superhero(in)es ready for action

- Standing position
 - Weave your fingers (in the same way as in chest compressions) with your arms strained in front of you
 - As you breathe in, lift your arms up above head
 - Drop the arms powerfully and breath out while shouting out loud "Ha"
- Repeat 3-5 times.

Notes: "Ha" while breathing out comes from the stomach.

*Instead of "breathe in" use "have a smell" for 6-8 years old.

Introductory Breath (3)

Fear go away

- Sit squatting
 - Smile with the teeth shut down and eyes popped out (as in picturing fear)
 - Breathe in through the mouth
 - Shut the mouth and hold the air in for a while
 - Exhale slowly from the nose
- Repeat 3-5 times.

Notes: While children are holding their breath, they are thinking of controlling their fear and while exhaling they are sending their fear away. This breathing exercise can be connected to both safety check and emotional complicity (FFF). Children are now ready to act.

Introductory Breath (4)

Color your Breathing

- Ask the children to imagine a color they like.
- Now, to visualize it filling their whole body while inhaling (take 7 deep breaths).
- Then, give a black paper to each and ask them to paint it with the color they imagined.
- Next, the children gather to form a circle. They unite their creations on the floor. We stop and observe this collective creation.
- We discuss the feeling of how something we imagined, has turned into a form of reality and has actually become a part of something bigger (the power of acting).

Begin - Warm Up-Physical

A sequence of unexpected events

With music on, children are walking in any direction following the teacher's instructions. E.g. -Be careful! Thumbtacks! On your toes, don't step on them! -Oh, no! You did step on some, now you can walk only on your heels! -The ground opened in two! Walk with your feet wide open or you will fall in the hole! -Ok, you passed the holes...Now the ground is full of mud, so sticky you can barely get your foot off of it...Watch! Over your shoulders there are wings...your wings! You can fly! Go over the mountains, through the hills, feel the air on your cheeks, spin through the air...oh no, so much for your wings...they are gone...you fall to the ground.

You get up with your feet tied...Jump! You finally untie the rope...free! Oh no! Your mum had ordered you milk to make a huge cake and the store is about to close...you are in a rush! You finally find the milk...no, you passed it! You have to go backwards...there it is! You need to take lots of liters...In your rush, you didn't get a basket, so you have to hold them but they are so heavy you can barely move...oh, no, wet floor! The milk falls off your hands and you are slipping all over...right before your dream ends, fortunately you become a white horse and fly happily to your homeland while the sun is setting.

Warm Up-Personal

Dancing breath / heartbeat

Children are walking freely. They are asked to listen carefully to their breath/types of breath (or heartbeat). "Can you dance while walking?" "Move only your head." "Now add one arm." "And the other." "Your belly!" "Your nose!" "One foot." "And the other." "Altogether now!" "How do you feel your breath?" "Let's make some steps in the same position" "Now?" "Let's run!" "How is your breath now?" "Let's do some jumping dance!" "Now fall to the floor and sleep." "Can you dance while lying on the floor?" "Slowly at first and then faster." "Now step up and feel your heartbeat."

Notes: The teacher emphasizes that any movement is the "right" movement. In case of hesitation, children can choose a pair.

Warm Up-Team

Our hearts beat as One/ Breathe as One

The teachers play the LIFEFORCE song (100-120 beat/minute). Children (either or both of the following):

- Sit in circle and following the beat, first they clap their hands and then hit at the same time with their right hand the next child's knee and with the other hand their own knee. Repeat until one united outcome, one sound.
- Form a spiral (representing a huge heart) holding hands. Then, they tune into the rhythm of the LIFEFORCE song, jumping altogether in that beat, until they jump and sound as one.

Begin - Unblocking Games

1. How many steps?

The teacher hits the defi or maracas and the children have to make as many steps as the number of the hits they heard. It is suggested that the teacher forms the number 1-1-2 (or 1-6-6) and asks for the children to recognize it. The teacher may also ask the children to count how many tens of hits they heard (depending on the age level: 1, 2 or 3 tens) and make the corresponding steps in the 100/120 beat/minute LIFEFORCE rhythm (with the help of the LIFEFORCE song).

2. Catch the rhythm!

Sitting in a circle, the teacher puts on some music with the CPR rhythm. The children have to hit their knees with their hands. It goes one beat per child and one child after the other, following the row as they are sitting, trying to tune in altogether with the CPR rhythm. After having acquired this level, next is to do the same but without the help of music. They now need to hold the rhythm on their own.

Confidence Games

Rolling on a human body

Children make groups of approximately six and lie facing the ground. The first child lies parallel to the wall and the next lies precisely next to it, without leaving any gaps. The same goes for the rest of the team so they end up lying one next to the other with their arms stretched, parallel to their ears. All heads to the same height. The first child lies onto the second and rolls slowly on the "human mat" that the children have created. Its arms are also stretched and parallel to its ears, it has to feel relaxed and not hold its weight and every now and then has an eye not to fall off the mat. As soon as it reaches the end, it lies facing the ground, next to the last child, leaving no gaps. Now it is the second child's turn, until every child has completed its turn.

Notes: Children that don't want to participate in this activity, will be the observers and share their observations in the end of the activity. The teacher should remind that a body that is stressed, stretched and afraid is always heavier than a body relaxed that can let its weight onto the team.

MAIN

In the Main Session, teachers have a variety of choices in order to build children's basic knowledge regarding the CPR information that children need to know and comprehend in an as much of a holistic way is possible, through multiple different thematics and elements. **More specifically, teachers can choose one or some of the following thematics to apply in their lesson:**

- Body Anatomy
- Vocabulary
- Social-Emotional skills
- Breathing Games
- LIFEFORCE BLS Algorithm
- LIFEFORCE Songs
- LIFEFORCE Yoga poses & games
- Language-Communication skills
- Cognitive-Perceptual skills

Body anatomy

Learning

- The teacher uses collocated verbs which accompany each part of the body, showing/depicting with their own bodies in which part they are referring to.
- S/he asks the children to participate by adding some verbs of their own. For example, Cheek goes with feel, touch, pinch, etc., Nose goes with breathe, smell, close, etc., (also define soft part of the nose), Forehead goes with hold, burn, etc., Chin goes with lift, etc., Ears go with listen, pull, etc., Shoulder goes with lift, push, etc., Chest goes with expand, shrink, etc., Shoulder blades go with open, stretch, kiss, etc. Lungs go with breathe, burn, exercise, etc., Heart goes with beat, pulse, sound, transplant, etc., Belly or Abdomen (top/bottom) goes with breathe, expand, etc., Navel goes with connect, etc., Palms go with hold, touch, press, feel, join, etc., Fingers go with stretch, bend, touch, feel, etc., Index finger goes with show, etc., Elbows go with (un)fold, bend, stretch, etc., Knees go with bend, stretch, walk, sit, etc., Feet go with move, etc.
- Children should be able to show Head Extension.
- Main target is for the children to connect each body part with its meaning word.
- Body parts should be taught few at a time (approx. 10 words per lesson).

Games

- **Sticker Game:** Children are divided in two groups. The teacher writes on the table the body parts the children learned earlier and gives each child from the same group a different word to copy on a white sheet, which they then cut with their scissors. Each group, making pairs with the other, has to stick (with sticking tape) the word they previously cut on the right body part of their pair. This happens in rotation for the two groups, so that all children have stuck their body part.
- **Music Game:** The teacher puts some playful music on and lets the children move freely or dance in the space. When the teacher stops the music, s/he names a part of the body (from the ones the children have previously learned) and the children have to freeze touching the exact part of the body that the teacher asked.
- **Little statues Game:** A child turns his/her back to the rest of the class and faces a wall. S/he shouts "1,2,3..." and adds a body part that s/he chooses while turning the other way. The rest of the children are standing the one next to the other in a row and run towards the child facing the wall while s/he is saying the above lines to them. The moment s/he stops and turns the other way facing them, they have to stop and perform the yoga pose standing still until s/he turns the other way. Any child who moves, gets out of the game. When the children approach the one facing the wall and touch him/her, s/he chases them till the line of start. The one who gets caught is the one who turns to the wall on the next round.

Vocabulary

The aim of the activities is to conquer, integrate and generalize on the new vocabulary, so as to use it functionally in all conversational situations.

- **Learning**

Introduce up to 5 words/concepts each time. Describe in detail the characteristics of each image. Ask all the pupils in turn to describe them. Explain the use of objects and the action of the heroes. Connect the vocabulary to the pupils' experiences by asking them if they know some objects/heroes. Let the pupils describe their experience.

- **Identification**

Match the images with the names of the items-concepts (with a visual aid). Find different image forms and let the pupils match them to the already known ones.

- **Semantic development**

Identification of objects/concepts, based on their attributes-characteristics. Give a definition of the words and/or talk about the target word in a circumlocutory way. Let the pupils guess the name of the word.

- **Visualization**

Visualize the meaning of the word with gestures and pantomime.

- **Connect the image with the word.**

Play games on the whiteboard or verbally, with syllable/letter synthesis and analysis, in order to create the target word. After you have synthesized the word, ask the pupils to write it down on their handbooks and to draw the respective images (captions to images).

- **Thematic classification**

Depending on the stage you are teaching, introduce the already known respective vocabulary, as well. Ask questions and encourage the pupils to use the specialized vocabulary when answering.

- **Written language production**

Pupils write the definition of the word they choose and they describe the object/hero, respectively.

- **Generalization of new concepts**

Classification of objects-heroes, based on the classification of their characteristics and creation of new categories. (without visual aid)

Controlled rate of repetition, for the consolidation of words.

Enhancement of vocabulary use, with classification activities (odd one out). By expanding to the wrong use of tools or objects and to wrong actions by persons.

- **Vocabulary automation**

Expansion of the use of words to varying communication circumstances.

Use of vocabulary through pupil practice in simulation scenarios of emergencies.

Airway Obstruction

Breathing

12:02

**CALL
112**

Chain of Survival

Compressions

CPR

Emergency Number

Emergency Medical
Services

HELP!

HILFE!

AIUTO!

ΒΟΗΘΕΙΑ!

Safety

Listen

for Breath

Dispatcher

Look

for Chest movement

Responsive

Unresponsive

Feel

Air on our cheek

Bystanders

Social-Emotional skills

- Every child is unique and has his/her own temperament, abilities, experiences and needs. Thus, it is pointless to compare children with each other. Nevertheless, diversity provides a lot of opportunities for enriching emotional experiences.
- Children love playing games and games create a great bridge that allows us to approach them. Apart from that, playing games enables children to **experiment, become aware of their strengths and difficulties, cooperate with each other, cultivate skills and enjoy life!**
- Whenever children reveal parts of their personal experiences, we are open to hear them and provide a safe environment for sharing by **ensuring respect and confidentiality.**
- We always try to protect children's personal space and in case we feel that a child needs more space to talk about an experience, we can share our thoughts with our colleagues/ school principal/ school psychologist and his/her parents or carers.
- It is important to encourage children's participation, initiatives and **efforts regardless of the final outcome of their activities.**
- We avoid evaluating children's performance in activities, because there are no right and wrong answers.

We encourage good manners, cooperation, expression and sharing both verbally and non-verbally.

If negative or disapproving comments arise from one child to another, then we take the opportunity and we invite children to share their emotions and try to approach the situation from a new perspective.

We always keep in mind that we are role models for children throughout the learning process. In other words, they observe and imitate the way we behave, feel, speak, express and manage our emotions. So, it is crucial to be careful in our reactions and honest about our mistakes.

*younger children: 6-8 years old, older children: 8-10 years old

Material:

- 4 large Emotion cards, each one depicting 1 basic emotion (front) and 4 emotions categorized in zones of self-regulation (back)
- 3 large Fight-Flight-Freeze cards (front) and related questions (back)
- LIFE FORCE-map of emotions (poster with 40 emotions)
- 8 large cards with Social-emotional skills Scenarios (front), their brief descriptions and relevant questions (back)
- Emotions Board Game

Emotional awareness

1. The happy-sad butterfly

Preparation: pencils, scissors, A4 papers, paints, large paper, glue
We suggest children to draw a butterfly, fold it in half and paint one half with colors depicting joy and the other half with colors depicting sadness. Younger children cut and join their halves, thus making happy and sad butterflies. Older children work in pairs and are asked to draw other butterflies as well, such as the love-hate/ disgust-pleasure/ anger-peace butterfly etc. At the end, all butterflies can be glued to a large piece of paper on the wall.

2. Emotion Hunters

Preparation: 2 sets of emotion cards

We scatter cards depicting emotions in different parts of the class room and invite children, divided into 4-5 groups, to look for them. Each group discusses its cards, what emotions they depict and what situations are related to them.

3. Portrait painter

Preparation: see pupil's handbook

We give children a printed face to draw his/ her features and ask them to give us information about this person, such as name, age, gender, favorite game, thoughts and emotions. Older children are asked to write a short story about this person.

4. Actors for a while

Preparation: see pupil's handbook

Preparation: 3 sets of emotion cards

We scatter cards with emotions flipped over on the floor, making sure that every 3 cards present the same emotion. When we give the signal, children move in the space, take a card and then, look for other children with the same emotion in order to form small groups. Then, each group represents its emotion to others, who are trying to guess it. At the end, all groups vote for the most successful representation.

5. Our fears in a hat/box

Preparation: pencils, A4 papers, paints, hat/box

We ask children to draw a personal fear on a A4 paper. Then, we ask them to fold it in half and throw it in a hat/ box. After that, we sit in a circle, shuffle the folded papers and each child gets one, unfolds it and tries to find out what the child who made the painting is afraid of. Older children can suggest ways of dealing with the fearful situation.

JOYFUL

HAPPY

PEACEFUL

SAFE

CONTENT

ANGRY

IRRITATED

DISLIKING

AGGRESSIVE

PANICKED

FEARFUL

ANNOYED

ANXIOUS

STRESSED

JEALOUS

SAD

DISAPPOINTED

PAINED

TIRED

BORED

Empathy

1. Storytellers

Preparation: music, objects, 1-2 sets of emotion cards

Children stand in a circle. While listening to low background music, they walk in the classroom, choose an object and then, they place their objects in the center of the circle. Subsequently, each child chooses an object - preferably not the one they brought. After that, they form groups of four or five and compose a short story, based on the objects they have chosen. Older children compose their stories based on emotion cards as well. When their stories are ready, they share them in plenary.

2. Make me happy

Preparation: scenarios written in small papers, A4 papers, pencils

Children are divided into groups of 4-5. One child from each group has a problem and asks his/ her peers to say or do something in order to help him/her dealing with that. In younger children, we give prepared scenarios, such as "making mistakes in exercise", "being teased by peers", "parental illness", "lost game" etc, while older children are asked to write and play their own scenarios based on their ideas.

3. I like your...

Children are sitting in a circle. Each child turns to the next one on the left and says something good about their appearance, character or behavior. The other children listen carefully. After all children have spoken, the game starts again towards the opposite direction of the circle.

4. Same and different

We sit in a circle and give successive instructions to children, e.g. "Those who have brown hair, take a step forward!" or "Those who struggle waking up in the morning, clap your hands!". In younger children, our instructions are related to their appearance or general preferences, while in older children, our instructions refer to their character, emotions or relationships.

5. Treasure hunt!

Preparation: a small object

Children are divided into two groups. One group leaves the classroom, while the other is hiding an object, which has been agreed upon. When the first group returns, its members begin the treasure hunt. The second group helps the first group find the treasure by expressing emotions of joy, when the first group approaches the treasure and emotions of sadness, when it moves away from the treasure or vice versa.

Self-regulation

1. Zones in rolls

Preparation: rolls of toilet paper - 4 for each child, acrylic paints or crayons, markers, 1 set of emotion cards. We ask children to paint 4 rolls of toilet paper, according to the colors in the zones of self-regulation (blue, green, yellow, red). Then, we ask them to write the emotions or draw the facial expressions that belong to each one of the corresponding roll zones.

2. Abandon ship!

Preparation: A4 paper, pencils

We divide children into three large groups, all of which have the same scenario. Each group is on a sinking ship and has a life boat in which they are allowed to take only ten items from the ship. Every group discusses in order to decide which ten items they will eventually take with them. All three groups meet and negotiate the ten items they will take with them on the life boat, until they reach a final list of ten items.

3. Laugh-control!

Preparation: stopwatch

Children sit opposite each other in pairs. The first child tries to make the other laugh. After one minute they change turns. They are not allowed to touch each other and they have to maintain eye contact. The winner is the one who will manage not to laugh at all.

4. Statues

We play the traditional game, in which when we say "day", children move and express themselves in the classroom as they like, while when we say "night", children remain motionless, speechless, unsmiling as statues. We can pick a small group of children (about 4-5), who tries to make the statues move, laugh, talk, using funny words and expressions during the "night". Whoever moves, talks or laughs, loses and leaves the game.

5. What a mess!

All children -apart from two- stand and hold their hands creating a chain. The first child of the chain begins to tangle it by passing over or under the other children's arms, legs, etc., without breaking the chain. The others follow his/her lead without talking to each other. After all children are tangled together, the two children try to untangle the chain by giving verbal instructions. They are not allowed to touch the chain.

Fight-Flight-Freeze

1. FFF Pose!

Preparation: FFF cards

Children are divided into 3 groups and each one takes a FFF card.

So, there is the Fight-group, the Flight-group and the Freeze-group.

We discuss with children about the way each response is manifested (physically, verbally and emotionally). Then, we ask them to take a pose that represents it best. All groups vote for the best pose.

2. What if...?

Preparation: 3 wreaths and FFF cards

Children stand in a circle. In the middle of the circle we have placed 3 wreaths, each of which represents a different way of reacting to a dangerous situation. Thus, we have the fight wreath, the flight wreath and the freeze wreath. Each time we give our instruction "What if ...?", children run and enter the wreath that represents best their response to the situation we describe, e.g. storm, darkness, spider, bear, building top, cliff edge, accident, blood etc.

3. My FFF!

Preparation: 8 sets of FFF cards

We scatter FFF cards flipped over on the floor. Then, we invite all children to pick one and sit in pairs. Accordingly, we ask them to share with each other experiences in which they had the response depicted on the card. After listening carefully to their partner, children share their experiences in plenary. Older children can write their experiences and then, read them in plenary.

3. Rafts and crocodile

Preparation: large sheets of newspapers

We ask children to form three groups and we lay newspapers on the floor in three areas, each one representing a different raft. After that, we lead them verbally to imagine that they walk somewhere in Africa, until they see the rafts and go into them. Then, a crocodile is surrounding their rafts, which are being cut one after the other.

Children have to find ways to survive and play the rest of the story.

At the end, we discuss their reactions, physical, verbal and emotional.

FIGHT

-
1. Do you remember an incident in which someone had a fight response?
 2. How does someone feel when he/she has a fight response?
 3. Have you ever had a fight response? If yes, what happened?

FLIGHT

-
1. Do you remember an incident in which someone had a flight response?
 2. How does someone feel when he/she has a flight response?
 3. Have you ever had a flight response? If yes, what happened?

FREEZE

-
1. Do you remember an incident in which someone had a freeze response?
 2. How does someone feel when he/she has a freeze response?
 3. Have you ever had a freeze response? If yes, what happened?

Social-emotional skills Scenarios

- The social-emotional skills scenarios presented here are inspired by events of everyday life, which children and adults are constantly confronted with.
- The aim of the questions is to raise children's awareness and promote their training in developing social and emotional skills, which are necessary for their lives in general, but also in emergency situations.
- There are specific questions and answers related to each one of the presented scenarios, with escalating difficulty and complexity.
- The questions and answers related to these scenarios are indicative. Hopefully, children will come up with more questions and answers as they get acquainted with the procedure and the material.
- The more answers the children have, the more enriching and beneficial the activity becomes for them.
- It is important for children not to dwell on the obvious answers and to think about motivations / intentions / thoughts / emotions of the people involved.
- These scenarios provide children with the opportunity to imagine themselves in different situations and thus, get ready for future experiences or deal better with the present ones.

Scenario 1: Street in neighborhood

Description

A shabby man walks on the sidewalk and bends down to pick up a bill (distrust). A girl (Anne) is holding her broken skateboard (sadness, disappointment), while a couple is standing next to boxes outside the house they just moved (happiness) with a cat in a transport cage. A car driver is shouting and raising her hands (irritation) as she is standing in line behind other cars.

Emotions: distrust, sadness, disappointment, happiness, irritation.

Questions

- 1) Why is the female driver shouting? (irritation due to traffic jam) (L1)
- 2) How is Anne feeling? (sadness, disappointment) (L2)
- 3) How is the old man in the picture feeling? (distrust) (L2)
- 4) How are the man and the woman talking to each other feeling? (happiness) (L2)
- 5) Why do you think there is traffic jam on the road? (rush hour / accident / damaged traffic light ahead) (L4)
- 6) Why do you think the female driver is feeling irritated? (rushes to go on a date / finds it difficult to wait/ spends time on something useless) (L4)
- 7) What is the best solution to Anne's problem? (walking home / buying a new skateboard / contacting someone to repair her broken skateboard) (L5)

Scenario 2: Courtyard of school

Description

A student is covering his ears (annoyance) while being teased by two of his classmates (dislike) – a girl who is obese and a boy who has pimples on his face. A group of children – Kate, a very tall girl and Marco – is cheering for their victory in the middle of the volleyball court (excitement, contentment). A boy is sitting alone (loneliness) and the teacher walks in the courtyard (safety).

Emotions: annoyance, dislike, excitement, contentment, loneliness, safety.

Questions

- 1) Why is the boy covering his ears? (noise annoyance / peer teasing (L1)
- 2) What can you say about the child sitting alone? (has no friends / no desire to play / his team lost a game / he's been punished / he was hit and hurts) (L2)
- 3) What would you do if you were in the same situation as the boy being teased? (tell those who were bothering me to stop / ask for teacher's help / do nothing / go to a friend / do something I like) (L3)

Scenario 3: Department Store

Description

A colored boy is alone in a hallway (terror) while his mother -colored- is looking for him in another hallway (panic). A girl -from India- has fallen down and she is crying while showing the snack she wants (anger, stubbornness). Her father -white- is looking around (guilt), whereas an employee is placing products on the shelves (peacefulness).

Emotions: terror, panic, anger, stubbornness, guilt, peacefulness.

Questions

- 1) What happened before the colored boy found himself alone in the hallway? (something attracted his attention and he left his mother's side / she left him alone for a while, but he left the spot and they lost each other) (L1)
- 2) What are the causes of the girl's crying? (her father does not allow her to take the snack she wants / he does not allow her to eat the snack right away / she showed him the snack she wanted, but he did not respond immediately to her request) (L4)
- 3) What would you suggest the manager of the department store to do so that the employees are peaceful? (create a calm working environment / give them a satisfactory salary / discuss their problems in order to solve them / reward or praise the best employees) (L6)

Scenario 4: Restaurant

Description

A man of color has his mouth stuffed with food (delight, pleasure), while a woman is looking at the plate in front of her (disgust) and is shouting at the Chinese waitress, who is approaching (shame).

Emotions: delight, pleasure, disgust, shame.

Questions

- 1) Why does the man of color have his mouth stuffed with food? (gluttony) (L1)
- 2) How is the man of color feeling? (delight, pleasure) (L2)
- 3) What do you think will happen next to the man of color in the picture? (swallow food / spit food / choke) (L2)
- 4) How is the old woman in the picture feeling? (disgust) (L2)
- 5) What would you do if you were in the same position as the old woman? (call the waitress / complain to the chef / do nothing / leave the restaurant / order something else / leave that dish and eat the rest) (L3)
- 6) How is the waitress feeling? (shame) (L2)
- 7) Why do you think the waitress is ashamed? (she is about to apologize / she had a previous similar experience) (L4)

Scenario 5: Home

Description

A boy (Mike) is offering a bouquet of flowers to his grandfather, who is sitting in an armchair (joy, tenderness, surprise), while a man and a woman are embracing (love) and their dog is brushing against their legs (jealousy).

Emotions: joy, tenderness, surprise, love, jealousy.

Questions

- 1) Why is Mike offering a bouquet of flowers to his grandfather? (due to his birthday or name day / he was discharged / he's celebrating an anniversary / Mike wants to thank him for something) (L1)
- 2) What other way would you plan to show your love to a loved one, other than offering flowers and making a hug? (tender caress / offer chocolate / drawing / gift / verbally, eg "I love you" / kiss) (L3)
- 3) What conclusions can you draw from the behavior of the man and the woman? (they have intimacy / they are a couple or brother and sister or good friends or close relatives / they express their love / they are happy to know each other and have a good time) (L4)
- 4) What motive is there under the dog's behavior? (wants a hug / wants to go for a walk / is jealous of the relationship between the two adults / wants to be given attention) (L4)

Scenario 6: Beach

Description

A girl (Anne) is diving off a cliff and her friends –two boys (one is Nick) and a girl (Kate)– are applauding her (admiration), while a young man with physical disability is entering the sea using a ramp (strength). Two preschool aged children –a boy and a girl– are playing with the sand, when suddenly the boy grabs the rake from the girl (anger, jealousy, aggression).

Emotions: admiration, strength, anger, jealousy, aggression.

Questions

- 1) Why are children applauding Anne? (they encourage her in her first attempt to dive off a cliff / reward her risky dive / are impressed by her dive) (L1)
- 2) What can you say about the young man with the physical disability? (he likes the sea / has a strong will / is active and has interests) (L2)
- 3) What is the relationship that connects the four children in the picture? (friends / relatives / siblings / classmates / may have met on holidays) (L4)
- 4) What could be done to maximize the number of people with physical disabilities who have access to the sea? (increase ramp construction on main beaches / information on the location of ramps) (L5)

Scenario 7: School class

Description

Students are writing a test. One of them is looking out of the window (boredom), while another (Marco) is looking at his watch (anxiety, stress). At the same time, a student is trying to copy from her classmate (curiosity) and a girl has fallen asleep on her desk (tiredness).

Emotions: boredom, anxiety, stress, curiosity, tiredness.

Questions

- 1) Why is the boy looking out of the window? (due to boredom / thinks of something irrelevant to the lesson / something outside the class caught his attention / due to tiredness / imagines to be somewhere else) (L1)
- 2) Assuming you could help Marco have less stress, what would you do? (I would suggest to him not to look at his watch / I would tell him that it is important to think positively and concentrate on trying to write what he knows / I would tell him that if he does not do well in this test, he will have the opportunity to write better in the next one / I would hug him and share encouraging words) (L5)
- 3) What opinion would you form about the students in this class? (each student reacts differently to the same situation / each student has different needs and requires different treatment) (L6)

Scenario 8: Hospital waiting area

Description

A pregnant woman is sitting while her husband is touching her belly (optimism). An elderly man is standing outside the doctor's door while holding papers with medical results (sadness) and a crying girl is holding her belly (pain).

Emotions: optimism, sadness, pain.

Questions

- 1) How are the man and the pregnant woman in the picture feeling? (optimism) (L2)
- 2) Can you tell a reason for the sadness of the elderly man in the picture? (bad medical results or diagnosis for himself or a loved one / bad thoughts about the course of his health or his scheduled medical appointment) (L2)
- 3) What would you do if you were in the same situation as the elderly man in the picture? (I would try to have positive thoughts / I would cry / I would talk to the doctor or a loved one about how I feel and what I can do / I would not talk to anyone and would sit alone) (L3)
- 4) What could be done to reduce the pain that the girl in the picture feels? (take a painkiller / go to the operating room for surgery / physical examination and doctor's treatment suggestion) (L5)

Breathing in Circles

All children are standing in a circle.

Level A - Teaching

- The teacher exhales saying “a” and pauses within the same exhalation (at first 3, then 4 and lastly 5 times). S/he asks the children how many pauses they heard.
- Now the children take a deep breath, exhale, and whenever the teacher claps they pause and then continue with the same exhalation.
- Next, children are counting their exhalation to last for 10”, which is the sum of time they need in order to check for breathing in the algorithm.

Level B - Playing

- They make 3 groups and each child of the group takes a deep breath. While exhaling, the child runs round the circle and shouts an interjection that is expressing the emotion of fear of its choice until it is left breathless.
- The number of circles of each child and the total number of circles of each group is counted. When the sound of the interjection stops, the circle counting stops too.

Breathing Distinction Game

Level A – Teaching

- The teacher downloads a file with all types of breathing sounds on their mobile device (normal, fast, slow, noisy, agonal).
- They practice on each one of them together with the children, by listening to each sound and repeat.
- Then the teacher splits the children in 3 groups. S/he uses the breathing type cards and shows one to each group to perform. The group which is its turn stands in circle and the teacher in the middle of it, checking on them.

Level B - Playing

- Children are split into two groups.
- Each group has a leader who chooses one breathing type for the other group to perform.
- For a level of difficulty, each leader may command 2 or 3 breathing types to be performed in a row.

Normal

Fast

The image features a central square with a solid orange fill. This square is surrounded by a border with a diagonal hatched pattern in a light brown color. The word "Slow" is centered within the orange square in a black, sans-serif font.

Slow

A red square with a hatched border and the word 'Noisy' in the center. The hatched border consists of diagonal lines in a tan color. The word 'Noisy' is written in a black, serif font, centered within the red square.

Noisy

The image features a central red square with rounded corners. This square is surrounded by a border with a diagonal hatched pattern in a golden-brown color. The word "Agonal" is centered within the red square in a dark grey, sans-serif font.

Agonal

These activities are meant to teach the LIFEFORCE BLS algorithm Stages and Steps.

1. Preparation: One set of cards per class.

- Place a set of cards on the table.
- In turn, cards are drawn by the teacher who asks a pupil to answer.
- The teacher can direct the answer and provide helpful hints describing the answer, or asking the rest of the class for help.
- **If the question is still too difficult, either a new card is drawn or the question is passed on to the whole class.**
- The pupil with the most correct answers wins.

2. Preparation: One set of cards per team.

- You can create two teams. Each team has a set of cards.
- Each pupil draws one card and answers the questions on it.
- **If a question is too difficult for one pupil of the team, he or she can give the card to another team member. The other pupil answers the question or the card can be answered by the team.**
- The team with the most correct answers wins.

3. Preparation: One set of cards per 8 pupils / one set of cards per pupil.

The aim of the game is to be the fastest in finding the correct card in a pair of cards, (the teacher can give the scenario to each team and then ask which of the two step cards is the correct one. The team to answer more quickly wins. Alternatively, the whole class is asked the question and each pupil answers individually.

4. Preparation: One set of cards per pupil.

The teacher says the name of one stage and its steps, but either omits one step or adds one step from another stage. Pupils must perform the sequencing they hear and to locate and correct the error as fast as they can.

5. Preparation: One set of cards per team.

The aim of the game is to correctly guess cards. The team which correctly guesses the most cards wins.

Each team chooses one card and one pupil to present the card using pantomime. The other group must guess the stage the card belongs to and which card it is. The same can be done by drawing on the white board. Stages and steps are drawn and the pupils in the other team guess.

Phonological/semantic cues for each activity

- **Indicative cues (verbal and non-verbal prompts)** would be to give the initial letter /syllable/word of the target-answer.
- To help using pantomime, by mimicking the action
- To draw on the whiteboard

CHAIN OF SURVIVAL

This is not a separate Step in the BLS-Algorithm but more an introduction to the children, that they, by recognising a cardiac arrest, by calling for help and starting CPR are able to save a life together with others (EMS, doctors etc.)!

Step 1: Early recognition and call for help to prevent cardiac arrest and to activate the EMS.

Step 2: Early bystander CPR - to slow down the damage of the brain and heart, and to buy time to enable AED and EMS arrival.

Step 3: Early defibrillation - to restart a heart.

Chain of Survival

S1: Can you list the parts that are needed to save a life?(L1)

S1: Why is it important to recognize a cardiac arrest and to react early?

S1: Would it be better to wait for EMS without acting?(L6)

S2: Can you give a reason for an early bystander resuscitation?(L2)

S2: What would happen if you waited too long for CPR?(L3)

S2: What are the advantages of early bystander CPR?(L4)

S3: What happens when we perform early defibrillation?(L1)

S3: What is the function of early defibrillation?(L4)

S3: What would you recommend to improve survival of the victim?(L6)

Safety

SAFETY

Step 1: Ask yourself: Is the situation safe for me?
(e.g. traffic, electricity, fire, shards)

Step 2: Ask yourself: Is the situation safe for those around me?

Step 3: Ask yourself: Is the person in need safe?

Safety

S1: Can you write in your own words what dangers you have to look out for?(L2)

S1: What would you have done if there were a fire around the victim?(L3)

S1: Why is it important to look for dangers?(L5)

S2: What do you think you need to look out for?(L2)

S2: What would happen if the people around you were in danger?(L3)

S2: Would it be better to start with the bystander CPR without looking for safety first?(L6)

S3: Describe a safe environment for the victim.(L1)

S3: Can you elaborate on the reason that you have to watch out for traffic?(L5)

S3: What would you have done if there was heavy traffic around the victim?(L5)

Check for response

CHECK FOR RESPONSE

Step 1: Kneel by the side of the victim.

Step 2: Gently shake/touch shoulders and ask "Are you alright?"

Check for response

S1: What is the first step when checking for response?(L3)

S1: What is the main idea of this step?(L2)

S1: When would you end this step?(L4)

S2: What action can you add to make sure that the person is not responding?(L5)

S2: What would result if you acted without checking for response?(L3)

S2: Create a scenario to show how it works.(L3)

Check for
normal breathing

**CHECK FOR
NORMAL BREATHING**

Step 1: If the victim is not reacting (for example speaking or reacting to you), check for normal breathing.

Step 2: Place your hand on the forehead and the fingertips of your other hand under the point of the chin.

Step 3: Gently tilt the victim's head backwards, lifting the chin to open the airway.

Step 4: Place your head over the victim's head.

Step 5: LOOK if the chest is moving.

Step 6: LISTEN with your ear for respiratory sounds.

Step 7: FEEL the victim's breath on your cheek.

Step 8: Having looked, listened and felt for up to 10 seconds, ask yourself "Is this normal breathing OR is it only coughing, moaning, snorting?" A victim who is barely breathing, or taking infrequent, slow and noisy gasps, is not breathing normally.

Check for Normal Breathing

S1: What might happen if the person does not react? What should you do then?(L3)

S1: How do you recommend to check for normal breathing?(L6)

S1: Can you elaborate on the reason to check for normal breathing?(L5)

S2: What do you have to do with the person's head first?(L2)

S2: Give a reason for placing the head in this position.(L2)

S2: Predict which part of the head you should pay attention to next.(L5)

S3: Can you explain what is happening in this picture?(L2)

S3: What is the motive behind this position?(L4)

S3: What made the position of the first responder successful?(L5)

S4: Recall the first sense you must use to check for normal breathing.(L1)

S4: Describe your physical position.(L3)

S4: Suppose you cannot see the moving chest. How can you improve the situation?(L5)

S5: Can you distinguish between this step and the previous step?(L2)

S5: Would it be better if you only LOOKED to check for normal breathing?(L6)

S5: What went well in this situation?(L5)

S6: What action of control do you see on this picture?(L2)

S6: What do you think the first responder would listen for?(L4)

S6: What were the advantages of this step?(L4)

S7: What does it mean if you feel the victim's breath?(L1)

S7: What is the relationship between the victim's breath and CPR?(L4)

S7: Why was it important to also feel the victim's breath and not just look and listen for it?(L5)

S8: What questions would you ask yourself in this situation?(L3)

S8: Would it be better if the person were breathing very slowly?(L6)

S8: Do you agree that coughing is a sign of normal breathing?(L6)

Call for help

CALL FOR HELP

10.4

Step 1: If the victim is unresponsive and/or not breathing, or is breathing abnormally, ask a helper to call the emergency services or call them yourself.

Step 2: Stay with the victim while calling for help, if possible.

Step 3: Call 112.

Step 4: Activate the speaker function of the phone, if possible.

Step 5: Say your name, your location and what happened, and answer the questions that are asked on the phone.

Step 6: Stay on the phone, don't hang up.

Step 7: Send a helper to bring an AED, if applicable. If you are alone, do not leave the victim, but start CPR.

Call for help

S1: What do you do when no other person is around you?(L2)

S1: What might happen if you do not call the emergency services now?(L3)

S1: How would you improve this situation?(L5)

S2: Should you stay with the person when calling for help?(L2)

S2: Can you identify the main idea why you have to stay with the person?(L4)

S2: What are pros and cons of staying with the person?(L4)

S3: Which number do you have to dial?(L1)

S3: How would you classify the importance of this step?(L4)

S3: How would you end this situation?(L6)

S4: What does this symbol stand for?(L1)

S4: Do you think switching on the speaker is a good thing here?(L5)

S4: What could be an advantage of using the speaker function? In which situation?(L4)

S5: What would the emergency services ask you in this situation?(L2)

S5: How would you feel if you were in this situation?(L6)

S5: How would you improve the situation while making the call?(L6)

S6: Is it okay to hang up, after answering the questions?(L1)

S6: Can you identify the main ideas of staying on the phone?(L4)

S6: How do you think you would feel in this situation?(L6)

S7: Which one should go to bring an AED?(L1)

S7: How can you attract a bystander's attention to help you?(L3)

S7: Can you predict the outcome if you went to bring the AED yourself?(L5)

Chest compressions

CHEST COMPRESSIONS

10.5

Step 1: Place the heel of your hand on the center of the victim's chest.

Step 2: Place the heel of the other hand on top of the first hand and interlock your fingers.

Step 3: Keep your arms straight.

Step 4: Position yourself vertically above the victim's chest and press down on the sternum, 5cm-6cm.

Step 5: After each compression, release the pressure on the chest, without losing contact between your hands and the sternum.

Step 6: Repeat at a rate of 100-120 compressions per minute.

Chest compressions

S1: Describe the position of the first responder's hand?(L1)

S1: Why is it important not to place the hand on the belly?(L5)

S1: Would you remove clothes from the person's upper body or not?(L6)

S2: How many hands do you need for the following step?(L2)

S2: Do you agree with the action of interlocking the fingers?(L6)

S2: Why did Marco choose to position his hands like this?(L6)

S3: Why should you keep your arms straight during chest compressions?(L1)

S3: How do you check if your arms are straight?(L4)

S3: Would it be better if your arms were angled?(L6)

S4: Can you recall how deep you have to press your arms?(L1)

S4: Based on what you know, how would you explain the depth of the press?(L6)

S4: What would happen if you were not strong enough?(L5)

S5: What happens after each chest compression?(L1)

S5: Elaborate on the reason of the release.(L5)

S5: Is it an advantage or a disadvantage to leave your hands on the breastbone of the victim?(L4)

S6: Provide a short outline of the next action.(L4)

S6: Compose a song about the beat of the chest compressions.(L6)

S6: Would you recommend a compression faster than 100-120 beats per minute?(L6)

Ventilation

VENTILATION

10.6

Step 1: After 30 compressions, open the airway again, pinch the soft part of the nose closed, using the index finger and thumb of your hand on the victim's forehead. Allow the victim's mouth to open.

Step 2: Take a normal breath and place your lips around the victim's mouth, making sure you have an airtight seal.

Step 3: Blow steadily into the mouth whilst watching for the chest to rise for about 1 second.

Step 4: Take another normal breath and repeat it once more (2 breaths in total)!

Step 5: Continue with chest compressions and rescue breaths at a ratio of 30:2 until help arrives!

Ventilation

S1: After how many compressions do you ventilate?(L1)

S1: Can you identify the main events of the action in this picture?(L4)

S1: Can you think of another suitable title for this action?(L6)

S2: What is Marco doing here?(L2)

S2: Do you take a normal breath in this situation or stronger than normal?(L5)

S2: How do you make sure, that all the air is going into the person's mouth?(L4)

S3: What would you have done in the same situation?(L3)

S3: Can you propose an alternative if you do not want to ventilate?(L5)

S3: How many seconds would you blow into the victim's mouth for?(L3)

S4: How many times do you have to blow into the victim's mouth?(L1)

S4: Why did the ventilation happen?(L4)

S4: What is your opinion on ventilation?(L5)

S5: What does the action on the pictures look like?(L1)

S5: What is the relationship between the compressions and the ventilation?(L4)

S5: Why is it important to start chest compressions again?(L5)

AED deployment

AED DEPLOYMENT

10.7

Step 1: Look around you for the AED sign.

Step 2: If there is a second helper, one of you should get an AED, the other should continue CPR on the victim.

Step 3: If no AED is available, continue CPR.

AED deployment

S1: Can you list three elements of the AED symbol?(L1)

S1: Can you identify possible locations for AEDs?(L4)

S1: Based on what you know, how would you explain what an AED sign looks like?(L6)

S2: How many people do you need to use an AED?(L1)

S2: How would you rate the importance of using an AED?(L4)

S2: How would you organise further steps, if there were enough people to use an AED?(L3)

S3: Can you stop the compressions during this step?(L1)

S3: Why do you think it is important not to stop compressions?(L4)

S3: What would happen if you stopped the compressions?(L5)

Foreign body
airway obstruction

FOREIGN BODY
AIRWAY OBSTRUCTION

Step 1: If you see a person holding their hand around their throat and coughing,

Step 1.1: then encourage that person to cough.

Step 2: If the person is unable to speak and is struggling or unable to breathe,

Step 2.1: then support that person's chest with one hand, lean the person forward and apply 5 blows between their shoulder blades with the heel of your other hand.

Foreign Body Airway Obstruction

S1: Can you explain what is happening here?(L2)

S1: Why did this situation happen?(L4)

S1: What is the best solution to the problem?(L5)

S2: What would you do in the same situation?(L3)

S2: Identify the main idea behind the action of the first responder.(L4)

S2: Is it important, to demonstrate to the person how it is done?(L5)

S3: How is the choking person feeling?(L2)

S3: Can you make use of the facts to choose the further steps?(L3)

S3: What would you have done to help the person?(L5)

S4: Explain what Marco is doing in the picture.(L2)

S4: What would you have done in the same situation? (L3)

S4: Imagine you are one of the characters and write a diary entry.(L6)

Activities

PART A

Scenarios 6-8

These scenarios are very close to real life experiences of children and correspond to the place where training is based, so to avoid confusion: school is the main element.

PART B

Scenarios 8-10

These scenarios are very close to real life experiences of children but they make a step forward including public places in the city/village, not just devoted to children - as it happens with playgrounds - and home as a place where they spend time much more independently.

BLS Scenario 1 (6-8)

We are in the playground in front of the school, where usually children spend their time with mates after school time. A woman collapses and children can easily notice the event, as it happens close to the swing. People in the scenario: children, a nanny, a group of 3 adolescents talking around the benches, a grandfather and a mother, the woman who collapses.

Objects: There is a fountain, from the park you see a small street and school can be easily seen and reached, there are two litter bins, benches and playground facilities (2 slides, 2 swings, a small castle to jump...), and a small kiosk in the park.

BLS Scenario 1 (6-8)

Card 1 Safety

- 1.Can you list 3 things you should do?(L1)
- 2.How would you test that the situation is safe for you?(L1)
- 3.What would you recommend to other children if they come close to the woman?(L6)

Card 2 Check for response

- 1.Shaking the woman ´s shoulders and talking to her a good idea. True or false?(L1)
- 2.How could you place yourself to assess what is happening to the woman?(L3)
- 3.Why is it so important to assess if she is still responsive?(L5)

Card 3 Check for normal breathing

- 1.How would you describe the position of your hands and fingertips?(L1)
- 2.How could you realize if the woman is breathing normally?(L3)
- 3.Can you identify the main senses you use?(L4)

Card 4 Call for help

- 1.Do you remember the emergency number?(L1)
- 2.Who is the best person to call for help? (Choose from the picture)(L2)
- 3.What info would you use to explain to the emergency operator what's happening?(L4)

Card 5 Chest compressions

1. Do you remember what to do with your hands, while waiting for the ambulance?(L1)
2. Describe what happens when you have to do chest compressions.(L1)
3. What makes chest compressions successful?(L5)

Card 6 Ventilation

1. Do you remember how to combine compressions and ventilations?(L1)
2. Can you give a reason for ventilation?(L2)
3. What choice would you have made, if you were unable to perform mouth to mouth ventilation?(L6)

Card 7 AED deployment

1. What does an AED look like?(L1)
2. Defibrillation should be done within 3-5 minutes of collapse. True or false?(L1)
3. Can you assess the importance of using an AED?(L6)

BLS Scenario 2 (6-8)

We are at school, right during class time and the teacher collapses. Pupils are sitting at single desks, there are school bags on the shelves, three big windows on the left side of the room, and a door on the right.

People in the scenario: there are 20 pupils, the teacher who collapses, two janitors in the corridor and a teacher passing by the corridor close to the door (close to the classroom, he/she can easily listen to noises or calls). The teacher is carrying a lot of papers and books.

Objects: singles desks, a shelf for school bags, a table in the back of the room, teacher's desk is close to the first window in front of desks rows (4 rows, 5 students in each row), an interactive board and a blackboard, a medicine cabinet and a small shelf with tissues and a bottle of water with plastic glasses for pupils to drink.

BLS Scenario 2 (6-8)

Card 1 Safety

- 1.What are the questions you should ask yourself to check for safety?(L1)
- 2.Can you distinguish any potential hazard in the picture?(L2)
- 3.How would you test that the situation is safe for you?(L5)

Card 2 Check for response

- 1.What is the first thing to check when you kneel by the teacher?(L1)
- 2.How would you test if the teacher is still responsive?(L5)
- 3.Why was it so important to assess if the teacher was still responsive?(L5)

Card 3 Check for normal breathing

- 1.Do you remember where you should place your hands?(L1)
- 2.Can you explain to your new schoolmate how to act?(L2)
- 3.Can you identify the main senses to use to check for normal breathing?(L4)

Card 4 Call for help

- 1.Who is better to involve to call for help? (Choose from the picture)(L2)
- 2.What should you do if the person next to you didn't have a phone in order to call for help?(L3)
- 3.Why is it important to turn the speakerphone on?(L5)

Card 5 Chest compressions

1. Describe what happens when you do chest compressions. (L1)
2. Can you explain what happens when you put your hands in the middle of the teacher's chest? (L2)
3. What makes chest compressions successful? (L5)

Card 6 Ventilation

1. How would you explain the ventilation? (L1)
2. Can you list the main actions for performing ventilation? (L1)
3. How would you determine if the teacher was breathing normally? (L6)

Card 7 AED deployment

1. Do you remember the symbol of AED? (L1)
2. Can you give a reason for the importance of AED use? (L2)
3. Can you identify who could use the AED? Why? (L4)

BLS Scenario 1 (8-10)

We are in the small square of the village/city neighborhood when a young man collapses. A small group of 3 children notice the scene, as they are queuing at the ice cream kiosk in the square. They are queuing with a parent, accompanying the three friends.

People in the scenario: ice cream man, a parent, 3 children, the young man who collapses, a couple waiting at the bus stop close to the kiosk, a man with a dog passing in the square.

Objects: the kiosk in the square, the bus stop (with a bus coming to the stop), few cars in the adjoining street, two benches, a small fountain, a public case with the AED (donated to the community), there are few other shops like a flower shop, a pharmacy, a newsagent.

BLS Scenario 1 (8-10)

Card 1 Safety

- 1.What does danger look like?(L1)
- 2.What could be done to reduce the hazards present in this situation?(L5)
- 3.Determine who could help you in making the scene safe.(L5)

Card 2 Check for response

- 1.Can you list the main actions for checking the man's response?(L1)
- 2.What evidence can you find to understand if the man is responding or not?(L4)
- 3.What is the next step to take if the man is not responding?(L5)

Card 3 Check for normal breathing

- 1.Can you explain to your friends how to act?(L2)
- 2.Can you identify how to use your senses to check for normal breathing?(L4)
- 3.What makes checking for normal breathing difficult?(L5)

Card 4 Call for help

- 1.Can you describe to nearby people how to call for help?(L1)
- 2.Can you elaborate why it's very important to call for help?(L5)
- 3.What information would you use to describe the place where you are?
(L6)

Card 5 Chest compressions

- 1.Can you remember how you should press on the man's chest?(L1)
- 2.How are chest compressions related to saving the man's life?(L4)
- 3.What makes chest compressions more effective?(L5)

Card 6 Ventilation

- 1.Can you recall how long each ventilation should last?(L1)
- 2.What is the function of ventilations?(L4)
- 3.Based on what you know, can you explain how to perform ventilations?(L6)

Card 7 AED deployment

- 1.Can you describe an AED?(L1)
- 2.Where would you find an AED?(L2)
- 3.What is the function of an AED?(L4)

BLS Scenario 2 (8-10)

We are at home, in the living room, where a mother is smart-working and her two siblings are playing video games. The mother loses consciousness and lays on the floor, so her children immediately notice the scene.

People in the scenario: mother, two siblings

Objects: living room furniture, a telephone, a tv set with gaming console, a window and the smart-working table where the mother is sitting, some pillows on the sofa.

BLS Scenario 2 (8-10)

Card 1 Safety

- 1.Can you list dangerous objects in the room?(L1)
- 2.Can you decide if it is safe to go near the mother?(L4)
- 3.If there are no hazards around, what is the next thing to do?(L6)

Card 2 Check for response

- 1.Can you recall the main actions you should take?(L1)
- 2.How would you check the mother's response?(L5)
- 3.Based on what you know, how would you explain to your sibling what's happening?(L6)

Card 3 Check for normal breathing

- 1.How could you use your hands to open the mother's airway?(L3)
- 2.What evidence can you find to identify if there is normal breathing?(L4)
- 3.Suppose you could not verify if breathing is normal. What would you do?(L5)

Card 4 Call for help

- 1.Can you recall the emergency number?(L1)
- 2.Why do you think the operator asks you to stay on the phone?(L4)
- 3.What information would you give to explain what is happening?(L6)

Card 5 Chest compressions

- 1.Can you recall how deep you should press on the mother's chest?(L1)
- 2.What makes chest compressions more effective?(L5)
- 3.How would you prioritize chest compressions if an AED arrived?(L6)

Card 6 Ventilation

- 1.How many ventilation attempts can you perform before resuming chest compressions?(L1)
- 2.What makes mouth ventilations successful?(L5)
- 3.How can you help, if you can't perform ventilations?(L6)

Card 7 AED deployment

- 1.What can you do while waiting for the AED to arrive?(L1)
- 2.Defibrillation should be done after 10 minutes of collapse. True or false?(L1)
- 3.Why is the use of the AED so important?(L2)

Emotion-focused questions for BLS scenarios

- 1.How do people around the victim feel?
- 2.Whose place would you most like to be in and why?
- 3.Whose place would you least like to be in and why?
- 4.How would you feel if you were in _____ [Name] 's place?
- 5.What possible actions do you think _____ [Name] can take now?
- 6.Can you guess _____ [Name] 's emotions after each action?

Activities

Locate the sound!

- Ask one of the students to leave the room. The rest of the class decides where to hide a kitchen timer or a metronome (set to 120 b/m) or a mobile phone making sounds (playing a song, ringing, e.t.c).
- The student who was outside returns to the room with eyes closed. Being supported by a helper for safety reasons, moves towards the place he/she thinks the sound is coming from.
- Will he/she find the hidden sound? How long would it take?
- For increased difficulty, group members make sounds at the same time, causing partial masking to the target sound.

Who is the Instrument player?

- Make a circle, with all students facing the center. They sing a LIFEFORCE song and steadily clap to the beat with hands behind their back.
- One student -the leader- walks outside the circle and secretly places a small instrument (maracas, bells, claves...) in the hands of one of the students.
- The instrument player plays his/her instrument and continues to sing along with the singing and clapping of the rest.
- At the end of the song the leader asks another student: Who is the instrument player?
- Once discovered, the instrument player becomes the leader and the game continues with a different song.

1. LIFEFORCE BLS algorithm

Someone is lying, lying on the floor
I want to help, something must be wrong
I approach with safety and get on my knees
I ask 'are you fine?' and wait to see...

I don't get an answer, I check for normal breathing
by looking, listening and by feeling.
I call one one two from my phone
and I turn the speaker on, turn the speaker on.

Life is precious and it's sad if it's lost
so join the team of LIFEFORCE.
Help save lives, you can do it too
call one one two, call one one two
call one one two, call one one two.

I say my name and where I am
I describe the situation, I don't hang up
I stay by the person, I don't leave the scene
and I ask somebody to bring an AED.

I should not wait for the ambulance to come
The sooner the better, to start CPR.
I compress thirty times, blow two times
and repeat the cycle till the help arrives.

Life is precious, and it's sad if it's lost
so join the team of LIFEFORCE.
Help save lives, you can do it too
call one one two, call one one two
call one one two, call one one two.

Music: Christiana Adamopoulou, Manos Poulakis
Lyrics: Ioanna Etmektsoglou

2. LIFEFORCE Three Steps (Safety, Check for response and Check for normal breathing)

If you spot somebody on the ground
Take a deep breath, ask yourself aloud:
"Is it safe to approach, is it safe to approach?"
Check around you carefully and watch,
Check around you carefully and watch.

If it's safe for you to approach
kneel next to the person on the ground.
Shake their shoulders and ask,
shake their shoulders and ask:
"are you alright?", that's the right task,
"are you alright?", that's the right task.

If the person does not say a thing,
touch the forehead and gently raise the chin.
Place your ear near their mouth,
place your ear near their mouth.
Listen, feel and watch for normal breathing now.
Listen, feel and watch for normal breathing now.

Lyrics-Music: Christiana Adamopoulou

3. LIFEFORCE Call for Help and Find an AED

After having checked the person's breath
I call for help, I call for help.
If somebody else is there too,
I ask them to call one one two.

If I am alone I call from my phone
and I turn the speaker on, turn the speaker on.
I start CPR, I must not wait
while I'm speaking on the phone, I compress and ventilate.

I say my name and where I am,
I say the breathing is not normal,
I ask a bystander to search for AED
to find it, to fetch it, and bring it to the scene.

I answer all the questions, I listen and respond
and I am never the first to hang-up the phone
and I am never the first to hang-up the phone.

Lyrics - Music: Ioanna Etmektsoglou

4. THIRTY AND TWO (Chest compressions and Ventilation)

Don't you find a normal breath?
Call for help!
But do not wait,
immediately start
to compress and ventilate.

Press/release with hands
thirty times,
raise the chin,
pinch the nose and blow two times.

Compress and ventilate
till the medics come.
Thirty and two
you can do it too
yes, thirty and two.

I do CPR
I press and press and press and press,
yes I do CPR I do not stop,
I do CPR
getting ready to blow! (x2)

Lyrics - Music: Ioanna Etmektsoglou

5. RIGHT AND LEFT FOR ME AND YOU

When we face each other,
my right hand is your left hand,
my left hand is your right hand.

Face to face cross to find the same
right hands cross and shake, shake, shake
left hands cross and shake, shake, shake.

Right cross, left cross....
right, left, right, left
right and left and right and left and STOP.

Right cross, left cross....
right, left, right, left
right and left and right and left and STOP.

When I see your back side
our right hands are the same,
our left hands are the same.

Make a train, all move the same
jump to the right and HOP HOP HOP
jump to the left and HOP HOP HOP.

Walk straight, walk straight....
run straight... run straight
run and run and run and run and STOP.
Walk straight, walk straight....
run straight... run straight
run and run and run and run and STOP.

LIFEFORCE BLS Yoga poses

LIFEFORCE BLS-Algorithm Yoga Games

Little yoga statues

A child turns his/her back to the rest of the class and faces a wall. It shouts "1,2,3..." and adds a LIFEFORCE BLS-Algorithm Yoga pose that s/he chooses while turning the other way. The rest of the children are standing the one next to the other in a row and run towards the child facing the wall while s/he is saying the above lines to them. The moment s/he stops and turns the other way facing them, they have to stop and perform the yoga pose standing still until s/he turns the other way. Any child who moves, gets out of the game. When the children approach the one facing the wall and touch him/her, s/he chases them till the line of start. The one who gets caught is the one who turns to the wall on the next round.

Yoga masters

A child selects a yoga pose card and directs the other children explaining the steps to perform it. In the end children say what the name of the pose is. Another child continues with the next pose. The teacher makes sure all of the 8 yoga poses are performed and identified.

Sequence in circles

Children sit in a circle. One child begins by performing the first yoga pose while the rest of the children call its name out loud. The child sitting next continues with the second yoga pose and so on until they reach the eighth when they have to begin from the first again. The activity ends after completing one full circle at least.

Yoga stories

The teacher splits the class into two groups. Each group is given all of the yoga poses cards and has to make up a Lifeforce yoga story. The one group will perform its story to the other group by storytelling, acting and using the yoga poses in the correct order.

SAFETY

Safety

- Standing position
- Deep squat (knees open or closed)
- Stretch arms sideways and parallel to the ground
- Turn the head first to the left, then to the right and again to the left to make sure everyone (including themselves) is safe

CHECK FOR RESPONSE

Check for Response

- Standing position, legs wide open
- Breathe in and while exhaling lower the trunk forward until the spingets parallel to the ground
- Open arms in a parallel position to the ground as well
- Look at the victim and ask "Are you ok?" "Are you ok?"

OPEN AIRWAY

Open Airway

- Standing position
- Stretch arms above head with joined palms
- Bend trunk to the left while breathing in, return while breathing out
- Bend trunk to the right while breathing in, return while breathing out
- Bend knees
- Lower arms, one with the palm pushing on the victims forehead and the other with just the index and the middle finger (stretched and joined) pushing on the victim's chin.

CHECK FOR
NORMAL BREATHING

Check for Normal Breathing

- Standing position
- Bring hands to the waist and bend knees like wanting to sit down
- Knees should not fall forward, children should see their toes
- Children imagine they bend over the victim and say 3 times
Look-Listen-Feel

CALL 112

Call 112

- Squat sitting
- Children hold with both hands their left foot
- They pretend to call 112 with their foot-phone
- They bring their foot as close to their ear as they can
- They say Who they are (name), Where they are (which school & city) and What has happened (basic description)
- They change foot and do the same

SEND FOR AED

Send for AED

- Children bring their left foot forward with the knee bent, placing it between the palms, on the ground
- The front leg is vertical and the ankle is under the knee
- The back leg is very well stretched
- Children are like runners ready to go for the AED!

CHEST COMPRESSIONS

Chest Compressions

- Children sit on their knees
- They open their knees wide apart
- They put their palms on their knees
- They are ready to start compressions!

VENTILATION

Ventilation

- Children get on all fours.
- They keep their wrists under their shoulders and their knees under their hips.
- They take a breath and while exhaling they fold their head inside and look at their navel forming a hump while imitating the cat.
- By inhalation they raise their head, send their shoulders back away from the ears, straighten their back and imitate the cuddly cat.
- They repeat 4-5 times

What can you do to support language and communication with the pupils you work with?

In the classroom

- Check that children understand the language used and the instructions given.
- Ask them to repeat back what they think you said or what they need to do.
- Use visual and tactile approaches including use of real objects, practical activities, pictures and videos.
- Use non-verbal communication to support what you say to pupils.
- Give them time to respond to allow time for thinking.
- Use strategies to ensure a child is paying attention.
- **Encourage an ethos of asking for clarification.**
- Give them time for work planning.
- Support them in understanding what they have read and making inferences.
- Watch out for those with slow processing speed.

In their descriptions

- Recall and re-tell events, to initiate speaking.
- When talking to children, add one or two words to the sentence length they already use in their own talking.
- Speak with expressions, with a clear voice to communicate and support meaning.
- Give explicit structures for supporting narrative skills – stories should have who, where, when, what happened and an ending (see the pupil small cards).
- Encourage children to support each other's thinking.

In a dialog

- When talking with others, there are many rules one needs to consider.
- Help them to start and finish a conversation by modeling.
- Take turns and not interrupt.
- Be aware of what the children already know or how they might be feeling.
- Change the conversation topic in an appropriate way.
- Be aware of the situation.
- Read the body language.
- Change the topic of the conversation.
- Know how to "repair" a conversation.

Non-verbal communication

Basic features

- Facial expressions
- Gestures and movement
- Pauses, volume, pitch, and tone of voice
- Eye contact
- Space and how we use it
- Body language and body posture

Activity 1

Form pairs of pupils and assign each pair a topic, which they will discuss in turn for 3 minutes. Ask the pupils in the audience if the conversation involved non-verbal communication, and then ask them to recognize nonverbal features in the conversation, and to identify the features that were absent, using the **CS-01 Small card**.

Activity 2

Preparation: Cut several strips of paper. On each, write down a mood or emotion like anger, joy, aggression, fear, annoyance, sadness, boredom, anxiety. Fold the strips of paper and put them into an open container. Write the sentence "Please stop what you are doing, stand up and walk in an orderly fashion to the front yard. Take only your jackets/coats with you!" on the whiteboard.

Have each pupil take a strip of paper and read out the sentence, expressing the mood / emotion they have selected.

After each pupil has read their sentence, the other pupils should guess the emotion of the reader. Each pupil should write down assumptions they made about each "speaking" pupil.

Prosody

Basic features of speech

Pause, pitch, stress, volume and tempo*

Activity 1

Preparation: Write the following sentence on the whiteboard: “You go to a party and you run into a classmate who has moved to a different school”.

Give the pupils in turn instructions like the following and ask them to act in the way described in it:

You are glad to see them. You speak to them with enthusiasm.

You don't feel like talking to them, but you pretend to be excited.

You don't like them very much, so you speak in a bored manner.

You are not fond of them, but you behave politely.

You don't like them, so you speak ironically all the time.

You are so glad to find them that you speak very excitedly and using a lot of gestures.

Activity 2

Ask the pupils to read sentences/a story using different voices from the **CS-02 Small card** (Whisper, Monster, Mad scientist, Silly, Old person, Mouse, Robot, Nasal voice, Quick pace, Slow pace, Baby voice, Pirate).

Alternatively, you can use the **Level 1 Prosody exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**.

For Level 2, ask the other pupils to identify basic prosody features.

* Please prepare sentences, which you will read to Level 2 pupils, first without a certain feature (i.e. pause) and then with it. Discuss similarities and differences, to help them understand what each feature sounds like.

Questions

Effective questioning

Key features:

- Use open questions and encourage pupils to discuss, not short answers (Ws questions)
- Use wait time (time to think)
- Respond to pupils' question with another question, so they will make appropriate connections
- Ask your pupils to form questions according to the learning task

Activity 1

Choose a topic and write it on the whiteboard. Instruct pupils to get information on the topic by asking "W" questions (why, who, what, when, where), which they can find on the **CT-08 Small card**.

Activity 2

Ask a pupil to think of a person (i.e. favorite artist, comic her or movie character) and then to ask the rest of the class, "Who am I?".

The other pupils must use both open-ended and close-ended questions to find the correct answer.

Activity 3

Ask a pupil to choose an object. The rest of the class takes turns asking closed-ended questions (answered with yes/no), to determine what the object is. If the class has not guessed the object, after each pupil has asked one question, then the pupil who chose the object wins.

Activity 4

Tell a pupil to ask the rest of the class who else shares a trait, quality, like, dislike, hobby, sport, etc. with them. For example:

- Who has younger siblings like me?
- Who likes (sport) like me?
- Who likes wearing (color) like me?
- Who likes (flavor) ice cream like me?

The pupil asks these type of questions until they find other pupils who have something in common with them. Then another pupil takes over.

Activity 5

Preparation: Find a story. Write down sets of open-ended questions (that can't be answered with yes or no) related to the story and their answers on an A4 sheet.

Read the story to the pupils. Write one answer at a time on the whiteboard.

Ask the pupils to find the correct question, using the **CS-04 Small card**.

Sample open ended questions

- How do (character) know that...?
- What do (character) think would happen if/after/next...?
- How did that happen?
- What could (character) do instead?
- How did (character) do that?
- Is there anything else (character) could use?
- Why did (character) choose that?
- How are these the same/different?
- Why is it important?

Conversational skills

Activity 1

Ask each pupil in turn to talk about 5 objects in the room with either a specific color, shape, material or function, which you will specify (i.e. 5 yellow objects). Each pupil has 30 seconds to list the 5 objects.

Then, the pupil names another color or shape or material or function, for the next pupil to speak. Each new speaker repeats 2 objects that they heard from the previous speaker and then talks about 3 new objects.

Activity 2

Write a topic on the whiteboard. Take a whiteboard marker and explain to pupils that it will act as a "microphone" to indicate the pupil whose turn it is to speak. All other pupils must listen. Give the marker to the pupil who will speak first and ask them a question about the topic. The pupil will answer the question and then must ask a different question to the pupil who will speak next (what, who, how, why, when, where) about the same topic and pass the marker. Each speaker must answer the question and then ask a different question about the topic, passing on the marker.

Activity 3

Break the group down into pairs. Each pupil in the pair picks one topic from the **CS-03 Small card**.

The pair decides who talks first. Explain that the pupils must establish eye contact and listen to each other carefully.

Remind the pupils that they should wait for their turn to speak, not interrupting their partner.

Tell pupils to begin by asking a question (Who, what, why, when, where).

Let the conversation flow and make the following comments at appropriate moments.

Instruct the pupils to stay on topic, by asking relevant questions.

Tell the listener to make a comment, to indicate that they pay attention.

Remind the pupils that, if they wish to introduce a new topic, they should wait for a break in the conversation. Remind the pupils that they can close the conversation with: see you soon, I have to go to ..., it was nice talking to you, talk to you later.

Alternatively, you can use the **Level 1 and Level 2 Conversational skills exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**.

Activity 4

Break the group down into pairs. Each pair picks one topic they're going to talk about. The pair decides which pupil will talk first. The two speakers must follow the conversational rules, while all other pupils must listen to the conversation and answer the questions on the **CS-05 Small card**.

Descriptive language – guides

Describe an object

What is its name?

Where can we find it?

What is its color and shape?

What is its material?

How is it used?

Do you have one yourself?

How would you use it?

Describe a person

Who is this person?

How do you know this person?

How is this person (face, body)?

What are they wearing?

What is their job?

Where do they work?

Activity 1

Copy the **Describe an object** guide-questions to the whiteboard. Choose an object in the classroom. Ask pupils each of the questions and let them come up with multiple answers. Enrich their answers with adjectives and other descriptive words*. Finally, give a complete description of the object, by answering all of the questions yourself.

The same activity can be performed with the **Describe a person** guide-questions.

*For each guide-question, write sample descriptive words on the whiteboard, denoting shape, color, size, material, appearance, expressions, senses and emotions.

Activity 2

Expanding on the previous activity, ask pupils to each choose one object in the classroom. Then, ask each pupil to give a complete description of their object, using the guide-questions on the whiteboard and to enrich their answers with adjectives and other descriptive words.

The same activity can be performed with the **Describe a person** guide-questions.

Activity 3

Ask pupils to describe an object or person familiar to them, using the **LS-01 Small card** and guide-questions, either verbally or in writing. You can also assist them by writing on the whiteboard the descriptive vocabulary you created in the previous activities.

Activity 4

To have pupils practice their skills in senses-based description, arrange **the five senses on respective columns on the whiteboard**. Under each column, add a list of relevant adjectives, encouraging the pupils to share as many adjectives as they can. Then, ask them to think of different ways to describe an object/or person, using one word from each of the columns on the whiteboard.

Activity 5

Preparation: Locate a set of 8-10 images/pictures.

Show the images/pictures you have prepared to the classroom and ask each pupil to choose one. Then, ask each pupil to share their description with the classroom without revealing which image/picture they are describing. The other pupils must try to guess the image/picture from the description.

Describe an object

Name this object and specify its type

Where can we find it?

What are its characteristics?

What material is it made of?

How is it used?

Have you ever used it?

Name other objects in the same category

Describe a person

What is this person's name?

What is your relationship with this person?

What are this person's physical characteristics?

What is this person's appearance?

What is this person's profession?

How does this person behave?

What do you feel for this person?

Note: Please use activities 1, 2 and 3 from the **LSL-01 Large card**, to introduce the Level 2 guide-questions for the different types of description.

Activity 1

Preparation: Prepare different sentences and write them on the whiteboard. The sentences should be simple and basic, with no descriptive elements.

Ask pupils to make these sentences more descriptive, using adjectives denoting shape, color, size, material, appearance, expressions, senses and emotions.

Describe a location

- What** is its name?
- Where** is it located?
- How** does it look like?
- Why** do we go there?
- Where** is a similar location?
- How** do you feel when you go there?

Describe a situation

- Who** is/are the hero/heroes?
- Where** is it happening?
- When** did it happen?
- What** is happening?
- How** are the heroes acting?
- How** are they feeling?
- What** happened at the end?
- What** was a similar situation that happened to you?

Activity 2

Ask pupils to each choose a topic and write a descriptive paragraph, **without using any "to be" verbs**. Alternatively, you may limit them to one or two per paragraph. Pupils should come up with alternative, more complex syntax to add description to their topic. Please also use the **LS-02 and LS-03 Small cards** and guide-questions.

Activity 3

Ask pupils to each choose an object and then ask them to write five sentences about it. Each sentence must focus on one of the senses. Pupils will have to come up with the appropriate vocabulary for each sentence.

Activity 4

Preparation: Prepare samples of descriptive and narrative texts. Split pupils into two groups. Ask one group to read the descriptive text and the other group to read the narrative text. Then, have the pupils compare and contrast the two types of text and write the main characteristics of each on the whiteboard.

Key Elements of a Narrative

Choose a topic

Instruct the pupils to think about real life experiences and make a list of the things that they want to include in their stories.

Create character(s) and choose a setting

Ask your pupils to think of the main character(s) and their details (name, appearance, likes/dislikes, interests, place of residence, family, etc.).

Ask the pupils to make each a list of 3 adjectives describe their heroes.

Ask the pupils to think of the time and setting of their stories.

The Beginning

Advise the pupils to set an opening scene. It should grab the reader's attention with an unusual premise.

The Problem

Ask pupils to introduce the problem which the heroes are facing (is it a conflict with another character, with themselves, with a real-life/fictional situation?)

Suggest that there may be an unexpected twist to the story.

The Resolution

Ask the pupils to describe how the problem reaches its climax and how it is resolved.

The End

Ask the pupils to devise the end to the story and to think of what the heroes achieved/learned.

Activity 1

Draw 4 columns on the board: WHO (heroes of the story), WHERE/WHEN (setting), WHAT (does the hero want to achieve), PROBLEM (what prevents the hero from achieving it).

Ask pupils to think of WHO, WHERE/WHEN, WHAT and PROBLEM ideas, and to write them in the respective column.

Finally, ask each pupil to create their own story idea with the contents of the 4 columns.

*Using the **LS-04 Small card**, pupils can identify the basic elements of any story.

Activity 2

Preparation: A4 printouts of fictional stories.

Give pupils 3 different types of fictional stories.

Ask them to write the types of characters they expect to find in each.

Then, ask the pupils to match each type of story with the most unlikely characters and describe them briefly.

Activity 3

Ask the pupils to prepare key elements of a story. Provide the topic and ask them to think of the heroes and the setting.

They must decide on the type of conflict and come up with 5 problems.

Activity 4

Ask the pupils to list their 2 favorite movies and books.

Then ask them to find the main elements of each (WHO, WHERE/WHEN, WHAT, PROBLEM). Ask pupils to narrate their favorite movies/books, using the **LS-04 Small card** for structure. Alternatively, use the **Level 2 Narrative exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**.

Cognitive are the primary skills our brain uses to read, memorize, process, think, learn, reason, pay attention and move the muscles of the body. These skills start to develop from early childhood.

Training exercises work best when practiced 5 days per week for 8-12 weeks. Two or three activities can be completed in 15 minutes. Games are rotated, in order to work on all the cognitive skills.

Tips

- Discuss course schedule and prepare the pupils using their own experiences, to help them understand why it's important to learn.
- Allow extra time for skill practice.
- Allow trial and error to learn the skills. In your classroom, develop a culture where mistakes are a learning tool, and not a way to evaluate the pupils' skills.
- Repeat the information in as many ways as you can throughout the course (in the middle and at the end).
- Use a reward system (you can let the pupils select the reward system).
- Be on topic. Laugh and joke with them, but continue to steer them back to topic.
- Prefer black and white printing to increase the visual challenge of the games and plan for extra brain breaks.

Activities for brain break

Have brain breaks before, during, and/or after an activity. A brain break gets pupils refocused and ready to learn again.

- **Play Mingle.** Set the timer for five intervals, each lasting one minute. Each time the timer goes off pupils have to mingle with someone new. The teacher poses five questions on the white board to help get the conversation started.
- Follow the leader is a pupil favorite. Change this game up by having pupils take turns being the leader.
- Use skywriting to practice spelling or vocabulary words. Choose a word and have pupils write it in the sky.
- Pupils pretending to be playing different instruments in the air. It is a good way to get their energy out.
- Pantomime games.
- Establish a short thematic section in the pupils' everyday schedule, titled: "Our news". Every day, the pupils narrate in turn what happen on the previous day and what they will do today after school. Alternatively, they describe their news using pantomime and the other pupils must guess what the pupil is showing them.

Visual perception

Useful tips

- Use a coloured dot or sticker to show pupils what side of the page to begin writing on or reading from
- Use directional arrows to help students with direction or starting position for letter
- Use formation and dot-to-dot worksheets to formulate letters and numbers
- Highlight the line to encourage correct line alignment
- Encourage pupils to identify mistakes in written material
- Write the number of mistakes at the end of each row and give the pupils time to locate them.

Activity 1 - level 1

Use small cards and hand out one to each child, with a correct letter/word on one side and an incorrectly formed letter/word on the other side. Have the child try to draw/write the letter/word correctly, then turn over the card to see if it is right. (self correction)

Activity 2 - level 1

Use **VP-01 Small card** and ask pupils guess the pictures. This activity can also be used for writing letters and be color labeled for the early stages of writing. Please also use **Visual Perception Level 1 exercise 14 and Level 2 exercise 9 in the Pupil's handbook.**

Activity 3 - level 1

Preparation: A4 sheets of paper with dot grids.

Copy shapes in a grid of dots.

Gradually increase: the size of the grids with the number of dots, the distance from dot to dot, the placement of a grid next to or behind the child (she must turn her head or her eyes).

To increase the difficulty, remove some dots from the grid.

Alternatively, please use the **Visual Perception Level 1 exercise 13** and **Visual Perception Level 2 exercise 8** in the **Pupil's handbook**.

Activity 4 - level 2

Use the **RIGHT AND LEFT FOR ME AND YOU Song card** and ask pupils to recognise the concepts right, left on someone else (crossing of sides when the reference point is across him/her).

Rhythmically play with the song as couples, where pupils clap their hands individually among them, crossing them. They can also point to other parts of the body.

Auditory perception

Activity 1

Listen for the word & Listening comprehension

While reading a story, choose a word and ask the pupils to clap when they hear the word.

Read/tell the pupils a story and afterwards ask them questions about the story. (For level 1, ask for the basic elements of the story; who, where, when, what do they do, how, why, what is the main problem. For level 2, ask for more detailed information (quantities, location, relative position, names, etc.).

Activity 2

Ask all pupils to close their eyes. Then, tag a pupil and ask him/her to tell a story/describe an object, while all other pupils listen with their eyes closed. Afterwards, ask the pupils to use the **AP-01 Small card**, to describe the speech, and guess which pupil was speaking.

Activity 3

Preparation: Find small texts with narrative and descriptive elements. Use the **ME-10 Small card**, and train the pupils in each of the steps, namely Visualization (ask them to make a mental picture and describe/draw it), Chunking (Pause reading after 2-3 sentences. Ask pupils to recall what they heard), Paraphrasing (When you finish reading, ask pupils to recall the important information) and Repeat (Encourage pupils to ask questions/ask you to repeat parts).

This is connected to the **Auditory Perception Level 2** exercise in the **Pupil's handbook**.

Activity 4

Preparation: Compile lists of words for the different syllable structures below.

Analysis – Break a word into syllables or a word into sounds. Say a word and ask a pupil to detect and pronounce the sounds (not the letters) that make up the word.

hat — 3 (/h/a/t/), best — 4 (/b/e/s/t/), sweet — 4 (/s/w/E/t/),
through — 3 (/th/r/U/)

Synthesis – Pronounce the sounds (do not spell out the letters) that make up a word and ask a pupil to put them together into a word.

k-l-ou-d — cloud, b-l-o-k — block, s-p-r-i-ng — spring, p-A-s-t — paste

* To modify difficulty, start with 2, 3 and 4-syllable words with syllable structure of Consonant-Vowel (i.e. pony). Afterwards, choose words with clusters in the beginning, middle and end of the word (i.e. **Stain**, **master**, **fast**.). Move onto words with two consonant clusters, or a triple consonant cluster (i.e. **strong**, **hamstring**, **pastry**).

Activity 5

Predict information based on what was previously presented.

Describe an image from the textbook to the pupils, speaking slowly. In parts of the descriptions, omit main nouns and/or verbs (level 1) and function words (conjunctions, prepositions, etc.) (level 2).

Pupils must detect the omitted words and, depending on the content, provide suitable replacements.

Attention

Activity 1

Preparation: Find paragraphs/text of varying difficulty and length (number of lines, font size).

Give pupils the paragraphs/text and ask them to count (without reading the words or pointing at them), write down or say the total number of words. Compare the pupils' answers and repeat the process, until most pupils have found the correct number of words per paragraph or text. You can use the **AT-04 small card**.

Activity 2

Choose a spot inside the classroom. Split pupils into two groups and ask them to look at the spot for 10 seconds, without moving their heads or blinking their eyes. Whoever moves first, causes their team to lose. The winning team chooses the next spot.

The choice of spots should gradually change levels (over, under, left, right, straight, behind).

Activity 3

First choose a number, whose time table you want to teach (i.e. 4). Then ask pupils to take turns saying a number starting with 1, 2, 3 and so on. When they reach a number which is a multiple of 4, then they need to say BUZZ (or some other agreed word), instead of that number. The next pupil continues with the next number in the series as normal (thinking while listening for their turn).

Activity 4

Use the **AT-01 Small card**. Ask pupils to choose a letter and then write or draw as many words as they can, starting with that letter in the **Attention Level 1 exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**. Give the pupils 1 minute to do so. Remind the pupils that, if they need help, they can find categories of words on the back side of the card.

Activity 5

Use the **AT-02 Small card**. Ask pupils in turn to climb down the ladder (two, three or four steps at a time), starting from 100 down to i.e. 80, as fast as they can. The pupils can use the image for help. Gradually, you can increase the difficulty level, by increasing the range (i.e. starting from 100 down to 50).

Activity 6

Use the **AT-03 Small card**. Ask pupils in turn to say 3 things they can see, 3 things they can hear, 2 things they can smell and 3 things they can do, in one of the situations described on the back of the card, as fast as they can. Alternatively, ask the pupils to write the words in the **Attention Level 2 exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**.

Auditory memory

Activity 1

Read pupils a story or part of a passage and make deliberate syntax and vocabulary errors. Syntax errors may include sentence agreement (all the parts of a sentence should match. Verbs need to agree with their subjects in number and in person, etc.). Vocabulary errors may include out-of-context words. Pupils need to identify the errors.

Additionally, you can use the **Memory Level 2 exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook** and make descriptive errors.

Activity 2

Drawing with instructions. Ask pupils to make a drawing in their notebooks, following your instructions.

Example: Draw a circle in the middle of the page. Draw a tree to the left and below the circle.

Alternatively, use the **Memory Level 2 exercise 2 in the Pupil's handbook**, give detailed instructions (i.e. start at the top left dot, draw down 2 dots, then draw right 3 dots, then...).

Activity 3

Sequential recall of numbers and words

Read to pupils a list of 3 to 6 numbers in sequence and ask them to recall them in the correct order. Alternatively, read to pupils lists of 3 to 6 words and ask them to recall them in the correct order.

Activity 4

Ask all pupils in turn to say their name, favorite food and favorite game. Afterwards, ask questions such as, "What does X like to eat/play?" and "Who likes to eat [food]/play [game]?"

Activity 5

Mnemonic tools

Use the following tools to help pupils learn any new information.

a. Ask pupils to help you create a song or poem with the new information they need to learn. This can be achieved by setting the information to music.

b. Tell pupils a story. Ask them to visualize the new information from the story, and then draw a picture placing the events in sequence.

c. Ask pupils to help you create a story with the new information. This will enhance their memory encoding and retrieval skills.

d. Write on the whiteboard important keywords from a lesson, which the pupils need to learn. Ask pupils to help you create different acronyms (sequences of letters which may or may not form a word), where each letter represents the first letter of the keywords to be remembered.

Alternatively, arrange pupils in pairs to work on acronyms and have them present their results in the classroom.*

e. When a lesson contains an acronym (i.e. CPR), which the pupils need to learn, ask them to create a short sentence with words beginning from the acronym letters, to increase the likelihood of recalling it (i.e. Chicken Potato Rice soup).*

f. Give multiple pieces of information to memorize (telephone numbers, cities, recipe ingredients, shopping list) to pupils and ask them to recall this information using the chunking technique.

Explain that they must "chunk" the information into groups. The groups could be based on similarities between the pieces of information they need to memorize.

* You can use **Memory Level 1 exercises 1 and 2 in the Pupil's handbook.**

Cause-effect

Build the appropriate vocabulary (Pupil's handbook) and use the vocabulary activities.

Activity 1

Read a text or use the **CT-01 Small card**, and find causes and effects. For pupils with learning difficulties, ask closed-ended questions (answer yes or no). Mention the facts one-by-one in sequence and ask: Is it a cause? Is it an effect?

Activity 2

Read a story and ask pupils questions. Their answers must include cause-effect keywords, using the **CT-02 Small card**. Alternatively, pupils can write the answers in the **Cause-effect Level 2 exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**.

Activity 3

Ask reading/listening comprehension questions, using the following questions:

- Why did/didn't _____?
- Tell me what happened when _____?
- What causes _____?
- How did _____ effect _____?
- Explain why _____.
- Which sentence best tells why _____?
- What caused the character to _____?
- In paragraph _____ why did _____?
- If _____, how would the end of the story be different?

Decision making

Activity 1

Offer pupils two or more alternatives. Use the **Decision making Level 2 exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**.

Make lists of pros and cons, together with the pupils.

Make a connection between the pupils' choices and their consequences.

Activity 2

Give pupils a choice between two options. Your pupils have to answer one of the following questions and explain why (verbally or with pictures).

Would you rather:

be... or ...

listen to... or ...

have... or ...

go... or ...

live... or ...

make... or ...

learn... or ...

feel... or ...

Activity 3

Use decision making in a group debate (this should follow the debate activity in the **CTL-02 Large card**).

1. Select a debate topic. Form two teams of two pupils each, and ask each team to prepare speeches arguing for and against the topic, respectively.
2. Prepare the rest of the class to listen to the debate and use their previous knowledge on arguments to arrive to a decision. Then, each pupil in turn should justify their decision.

Argumentation

Activity 1

Pupils need to learn the following structure to present arguments, orally or in writing.

Ask them to:

- Choose a topic title, covering the whole topic
- Start with a question, presenting both sides of the topic
- Make an opening statement introducing the issue (give them brief ideas of both sides of the topic) - Prepare arguments for/against (using compare-contrast/ cause-effect) with supporting evidence
- Reach a conclusion (including summary and recommendations)

Activity 2

Debate (this precedes the debate activity in **CTL-01 Large card**).

Steps:

- 1.Create debate rules, (i.e. speak in turns, speeches last 2-3 minutes).
- 2.Choose a topic, brainstorming for ideas.
- 3.Form 2 teams, to argue for/against the topic. Teams must organize their ideas.
- 4.Have the teams prepare the speeches. Instruct them to note their points and supporting evidence. Teams end the debate summarizing their positions, with a closing argument.

Argumentation will be taught to all pupils, before they engage in decision making activities.

Problem solving

Activity 1

Read the pupils a story. Guide the pupils to ask questions, in order to get information about a problem. Use the following questions:

- why....?
- who....?
- what....?
- when....?
- where....?

Use the **CT-08 Small card**, or use the **Problem solving Level 1 exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**.

Activity 2

Read the pupils a story. Write the following steps on the whiteboard and use them to guide the pupils to identify and then solve problems.

1. What is the problem?
2. Ask questions/get information
3. Find solutions

Use the **CT-08 Small card**, or use the **Problem solving Level 1 exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**.

Activity 3

Ask pupils to each choose a real-life problem they have had to solve (i.e. extracurricular activities). Then ask them to describe how they solved that problem, using Side A of the **CT-09 Small card**. Alternatively, you can read them a story and they can use the **Problem solving Level 2 exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**.

How to solve problems

1. What is the problem?
2. What are some solutions?
3. Choose a solution and use it
4. Is it working? If not, what can I do now?

Logical reasoning

Activity 1

Form sentences using object properties, people's activities or information (i.e. events) from taught subjects, and ask pupils if each sentence is true or false.

Activity 2

Form "Can you do X?" type of questions, and ask pupils to provide logical answers (Yes/No), regarding the veracity of each question - **CT-04**

Small card.

Activity 3

Form sentences using object properties or people's activities, and ask pupils if each sentence is true always, sometimes or never - **CT-05**

Small card.

Activity 4

Ask pupils to answer if there is a correlation between the two notions in each of the following questions, using Yes or No.

If something is frozen, can it be hard?

If you celebrate something, are you having fun?

If something is fragile, is it strong?

If something is liquid, can it melt?

If something is sad, can it be pleasant?

If something is blank, can it be empty?

If you wear braces, can you open your mouth?

Activity 5

Show the pupils a picture (you may choose the LIFEFORCE BLS or emotional scenario pictures or use the **Logical reasoning Level 1 and Level 2 exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**), and ask them to answer the following questions. Follow up their answers with the question "How do you know this?", so that the pupils will need to justify their answers.

Alternatively, you may read the pupils a suitable text.

- Which season does the scenario/story take place in?
How do you know it?
- Where are the heroes?
- What are the heroes doing?
- What is the relationship among the heroes?
- What will the heroes do afterwards?
- How do the heroes feel?
- What could happen suddenly?

Activity 6

Ask the pupils to fill in the sentences with the proper words, exercising their verbal analogy reasoning. Use **CT-04 Small card**.

Activity 7

Ask the pupils to complete the word pairs with the proper words, exercising their verbal analogy reasoning. Use **CT-05 Small card**.

Spatial Orientation

Activity 1

Use the **OR-01 Small card**, to teach the direction of letters/numbers/symbols with visual similarities. Pupils write a letter/number/symbol in their text book. They place their hands to its left and right, respectively, and find the direction it points to. Alternatively, you can use the **Spatial Orientation Level 1 exercise 1 in the Pupil's handbook**.

Activity 2

Use the same approach to teach pupils spatial relations among objects. Using adverbs of place, pupils describe the location of objects in space. You may use the LIFEFORCE BLS and emotional scenarios large cards.

Suggested questions

- Is the ____ between the ____ and the ____?
- Is the ____ in front of ____ and next to ____?
- Where is ____ in relation to ____?

Activity 3

Use the "Right and Left for me and you" song, to teach pupils perception of left and right, when an object is opposite them (facing them).

Emphasize how directions cross (mirror) each other (i.e. the pupil's "right" is the facing object's "left").

Arrange pupils in pairs (facing each other) and ask them to follow the song, playing along with their hands.

Temporal Orientation

Activity 1

Ask each pupil to locate 2 objects around them. Give instructions, as in the below examples, using temporal markers, like:

before, after, first, since, while

- Point first at _____ and then at _____
- Before you point at _____, point at _____
- After you point at _____, point at _____

You may use the LIFEFORCE vocabulary, Yoga poses, stage cards, as well as countries/cities on maps.

You can also ask pupils to interact with objects in temporal sequence:

- Do _____, before you do _____
- First do _____ and then do _____
- After you do _____, do _____

Activity 2

Ask pupils to retell a part of a lesson, with temporal markers, placing facts in a sequential order. Help pupils' narrative, by asking questions about what happened in the beginning, before/after something, how did the story conclude?

You may create scenarios using the LIFEFORCE BLS stages/steps and ask the pupils to assume the role of the hero(es) and tell you what they need to do first, before/after a particular stage/step and at the end.

Alternatively, use **OR-03 and OR-04 Small cards**.

Processing speed

Activity 1 – Stroop effect

Preparation: On an A4 sheet write 10 sets of 4-5 words each, one set below the other, and color each word in different colors. Prepare 5 different A4 sheets, so that no more than 4-5 students have the same sheet.

Hand out copies of the A4 sheets to pupils and ask them to say the color of each word, not read the word itself. For instance when the words are “orange, blue, red, green”, the pupils must say “green, orange, blue, red”

respectively, as quickly as they can.

Alternatively, you can use sets like the following:

- Write the words backwards (parent - tnerap).
- Use non-color words such as “window” or “bicycle”.
- Use nonsense words such as “ouvir” or “zwat”.
- Use emotional words such as “fearful” or “happy”.
- Color only half of the word or color only the first and last letter of each word (towel, basketball)

Alternatively use the **Processing Speed Level 1 exercises 1 and 2**, and the **Processing Speed Level 2 exercises 1, 2 and 3** in the **Pupil’s handbook**.

Activity 2

Ask the pupils in turn to say the alphabet, each starting from a different letter. Do the same with the months of the year and the days of the week. Ask the pupils to use the **PS-01 Small card**.

Alternatively, you can ask the pupils to say the above backwards.

Activity 3 – Stroop effect

Ask pupils to use the **PS-02 Small card** or **PS-03 Small card**. For Level 1, instruct them to look at the shapes of animals and say the name of the animal, as fast as they can. They must NOT read the word written on the shape. For Level 2, side A ask the pupils to look at the geometrical shapes and name one shape and one color, alternately. For side B, ask the pupils to look at the numbers and name one number and one color, alternately.

Activity 4

Preparation: Make lists with series of 2, 3 or 4 single-digit and/or two-digit numbers (i.e. 1, 7, 14, 47).

Read each series out to a pupil in turn, and ask the pupil to recall them in reverse order.

You can make lists of syllables, words, nonsense words, instead.

Alternatively, ask the pupils to form pairs. Using the **PS-04 Small card**, one pupil reads out a series and the other pupil recalls it backwards. Then they swap roles.

END

Closing activities

When it is time to close the lesson, it is suggested to decompress children so that they feel both physically and mentally that the lesson comes to its end.

In the same way that pupils get ready to open up to new knowledge (through "Begin" section), they should slowly and gradually end this process inside the classroom, with the use of some techniques. This would lead to a smoother transition for the children to anything that follows and a better understanding and memorization of the desired material. It can be achieved with the help of the following activities.

End - Memory & Concentration Games

1. Sequence of Movements

- The teacher uses the stage of the Algorithm that has taught the children so far to play this game.
- Children are divided into 2 groups & the one is checking on the other.
- They are shown the card of the 1st step of the stage they are working on. One group performs & the other checks and vice versa. The group that begins first is different every time.
- Then, they are shown of the 2nd-step card, which they have to perform only after repeating the 1st (the previous step).
- The same happens with the 3rd-step card, which they perform after repeating the first & the 2nd step and so on
- Children have to remember the previous steps & in each repeat of that sequence, the next step in the row is being added by the teacher.
- In the end, children have to be able to remember & perform the whole sequence of the steps!

2. I went to the super market

- 1st Level: Standing in a circle, the teacher begins: "I went to the market & bought an apple" (a word beginning with the letter A) while making a relevant movement/gesture (i.e. biting an imaginary apple). The child standing next to the teacher continues with a word beginning with letter B, after repeating the previous word & movement ("I went to the market & bought an apple & a brush").

This goes on as far as it can, with the children adding and remembering objects and movements! Note: The teacher can use other themes too, like the beach for example.

3. I went to save a life

- 2nd Level: It is the same concept but instead of the supermarket or the beach, the teacher uses the stages of the Algorithm. So, for each stage, children have to say and show (with the right movements) the steps of the stage in the right sequence, one child at a time, with the next standing child to take the turn. Note: Whenever a child doesn't remember which the right step is going next, the teacher shows the corresponding card picturing the step.

4. What am I doing?

- Children are standing in a circle. The first child that begins shows an Algorithm step with the appropriate movement. The one sitting next to it asks "What are you doing?" and the first one answers by saying another step, different from the one that is showing. Then, the second child has to show with the right movement the step that the first child answered to it. This goes on, with each child asking the previous "What are you doing?" taking an answer (different from what it is really doing) and showing what is answered to it with the appropriate movement.

End - Relaxation/1

1st version

Sparkling Soda

- Children sit on the mat holding their knees
- When the teacher says “psss” they stretch both arms and legs and they fall on the mat in a relaxed way

Then, the teacher can choose among these 3-4 minute relaxation stories:

1.Senses in the woods

Fresh air is filling your lungs and your whole body. Close your eyes and feel the air blowing your face and hair. On the grass you see a crimson red flower. You bend and smell it. Next to the flower there is a butterfly, you lie on the grass and watch it going up to the sky. You notice its wings, they are glowing red and sparkle under the sun. The sun is hot and warms your face. Three little squirrels are playing in between your feet. They run towards the wood and you follow them laughing. As you run, you see in front you some red wild strawberries. You cut off one, you smell it and bite it, so delicious and juicy. Suddenly, you hear a river flowing so loudly next to you. It has very clear water. You drink some with your handfuls, it is nice and cool. You lie down, close your eyes and repeat from within “I feel safe”, for three times. Now imagine your body as it is lying on the mat right now. Begin to slowly move your fingers (hands and feet), come to your side, get up and sit squatting.

Relaxation/2

2.Focusing on our body

Imagine you are still/frozen statues. Bend your elbows & stretch them. Bend your knees & stretch them again. Move the fingers of your feet & leave them still. Raise your head & relax it. Move your eyes without opening them & relax them. Pucker your lips like wanting to give a kiss & relax them. Tighten the buttocks & relax them. Feel your whole body relaxed & slowly get up & sit squatting.

2nd version

Transferable movement

Children are standing in a circle. A child (or the teacher) makes a movement. Starting with the next child, the rest repeat the same movement, like a wave. The next child continues making its own new movement with the rest following and so on until all children have shared their movement with the other.

Reflection & Team Goal

Closing circle - Reflection

Each child answers while sitting in a circle, in turns.

- What did you like most of what you learned today?
- Describe your feeling of today's lesson in one word
- Describe the lesson in one word

Team Goal

• A two-line rime as a team goal or encouragement. This is composed by the present unit's knowledge and students' ideas and enthusiasm, e.g. "Go-go-go, Safety first for all!" Students repeat it loudly & rhythmically while joining their right or left arms in the center of the circle.